

Human Biomonitoring in risk assessment: 4th set of examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals

Deliverable Report

D5.11

WP5 - Translation of results into policy

Deadline: April 2022

Upload by Coordinator: 09 June 2022

Entity	Name of person responsible	Short name institution	Date [Received]
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Grant Signatory	Antti Koivula	FIOH	21/04/2022

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Acknowledgements:

We would like to thank all HBM4EU aligned study owners, whose data were included in the risk assessments, and everyone who provided comments on the draft risk assessments during their development. In addition, we would like to acknowledge WP10 and the VITO data management team for providing us the harmonized aggregated HBM4EU aligned study data, without which a large part of this work would not have been possible.

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2 Glossary

1-OHPyr	1-hydroxypyrene
3-PBA	3-phenoxybenzoic acid
AAMA	acrylamide mercapturic acid
AChE	Acetylcholinesterase
ADI	Acceptable Daily Intake
BaA	benz[<i>a</i>]anthracene
BbF	benzo[<i>b</i>]fluoranthene
BaP	benzo[<i>a</i>]pyrene
BE	biomonitoring equivalent
BHR	bronchial hyperresponsiveness
BMDL	Benchmark Dose Lower Confidence Limit
BPA	bisphenol A
BPS	bisphenol S
BLL	blood lead levels
BP-3	benzophenone-3
CHR	chrysene
CLP	Classification, Labelling and Packaging (Regulation EC No 1272/2008)
DALY	disability-adjusted life year
DAR/RAR	Draft Assessment Report/Renewal Assessment Report
DMA	dimethylarsinic acid
DMAC	N,N-dimethylacetamide
DMF	N,N-dimethylformamide
DON	deoxynivalenol
DPHP	di(2-propylheptyl) phthalate
EBoD	environmental burden of disease
EC	European commission
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EDI	estimated daily intake
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EHDPP	ethylhexyl diphenyl phosphate
ELCR	excess lifetime cancer risk
FIOH	Finnish Institute of Occupational Health
GA	glycidamide

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GAMA	glycidamide mercapturic acid
Hb-AA	haemoglobin adducts
HBM	human biomonitoring
HBM4EU	European human biomonitoring Initiative
HBGV	health-based guidance value
HBM-GV	human biomonitoring guidance value (derived within HBM4EU)
HDI	hexamethylene diisocyanate
HI	hazard index
HIA	health impact assessment
HQ	hazard quotient
iAs	inorganic arsenic
LB	lower bound
LOAEL	lowest observed adverse effect level
LOD	limit of detection
LOEC	lowest observed effect concentration
LOQ	limit of quantification
MRL	Maximum Residue Level
MDI	4,4'-methylene diphenyl diisocyanate
MeHg	methylmercury
MMA	monomethylarsonic acid
MoE	Margin of Exposure
MS	Member state (EU)
NCO	isocyanate functional groups (R-N=C=O)
NEP	N-ethyl pyrrolidone
NMP	N-methyl pyrrolidone
NOAEL	no-observed-adverse-effect level
NOEC	no observed effect concentration
OEL	occupational exposure limit value
P95	95th percentile
PAH	polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon
PAH4	BaA, BbF, BaP, CHR
PBPK	physiologically based pharmacokinetic (modelling)
PEQs	PFOA equivalents
PDI	probable daily intake

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PFAS	perfluoroalkyl substances
PoD	point of departure
PQ	policy question
RA	risk assessment
RAC	Risk Assessment Committee (at ECHA)
RCR	risk characterization ratio
RfD	reference dose
RPF	relative potency factor
SCCS	Scientific Committee for Consumer Safety
SLO	Slovenia
TCEP	tris (2-chloroethyl) phosphate
TCIPP	tris (chloropropyl) phosphate
TCPy	3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol
TDI	toluene diisocyanate
TDCIPP	tris (1,3-dichloro-2-propyl) phosphate
TPHP	triphenyl phosphate
TWA	time weighted average
TWI	tolerable weekly intake
UB	upper bound
OPFR	organophosphorus flame retardants

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3 Summary

The aim of this work was to demonstrate how human biomonitoring (HBM) data can be included in different risk or health impact assessment strategies. To achieve this, risk assessment (RA) was performed for the first and second lists of substances prioritised in HBM4EU: acrylamide, aprotic solvents, arsenic, bisphenols, diisocyanates, flame retardants, mercury, mycotoxins, pesticides, PAHs, PFASs and UV filters. In addition, environmental burden of disease (EBoD) calculations were performed for lead.

The overall result of the work performed during the whole project is that HBM data can be successfully used in RA, and its inclusion generally benefits RA, providing more confidence to it. A tiered approach can be applied, as described earlier in the HBM4EU deliverable report D5.5. When performing RA based on HBM data, it is important to consider the uncertainties involved. However, the main uncertainties are often not related to the use of HBM data itself, but rather to the dose-response and toxicological data used, making them universal to RA in general. Inclusion of HBM data may often in fact help reduce uncertainty in RA, especially if they are used to verify exposure assessment made by other methods, such as modelling. However, one of the major challenges for the inclusion of HBM into RA is the often-limited data available on toxicokinetics. In addition, in some cases, there is an urgent need for more specific biomarkers or more sensitive analytic methods than currently available.

HBM is an important tool in the assessment of exposure and chemical risks, as it gives information on populations' and individuals' total exposure from all sources and by different exposure routes. When performed on a regular basis, it may also give insight into time-trends of exposure, and therefore provide information on the effectiveness of regulatory risk management measures already in place. Other valuable contributions that RA using HBM data can provide are post-marketing surveillance, identification of emerging concerns, hot spot monitoring and raising awareness. Overall, it is therefore essential that up-to-date, high-quality HBM data are available for RA concerning both general and occupational populations.

While the RA/EBoD work presented here is not intended to have direct regulatory implications, the results can be useful for raising awareness regarding possibly needed policy actions, since newly generated HBM data, reflecting current exposure of the EU population, has been used in many of the RA/EBoDs.

These risk assessments have been performed within HBM4EU to determine how HBM data can contribute to the risk assessment of chemicals. The outcome of these risk assessments has no regulatory implications.

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4 Introduction

The objective of task 5.3 in HBM4EU was to perform risk assessments (RAs) and health impact assessments (HIAs) for HBM4EU priority compounds, in order to demonstrate how human biomonitoring (HBM) can be effectively used in chemical RA and HIA strategies.

In the first year of the HBM4EU project, the current use of HBM in chemicals RA was evaluated. In addition, examples on the advanced use of HBM under different regulatory RA frameworks were collected for HBM4EU's 1st list of priority substances (HBM4EU Deliverable report D5.1). To build on this work, RAs and HIAs were then performed in task 5.3 for selected substances from the HBM4EU's 1st and 2nd priority lists of chemical substances (HBM4EU Deliverable reports D5.5 and D5.8). The work exemplified different approaches utilising HBM data in RA/HIA, also demonstrating the benefits and challenges, applying HBM data already available in the literature.

Here, a final set of RA/HIA examples using HBM data are provided. Some of these are new RAs for 2nd priority list compounds, others are updates to RAs already presented earlier in D5.5 or D5.8, now complemented with new HBM data from the HBM4EU aligned studies. The new RAs cover acrylamide, aprotic solvents, arsenic, diisocyanates, mercury, mycotoxins and pesticides (pyrethroids and chlorpyrifos). Updated RAs were made for bisphenols, flame retardants, PAHs, PFASs and the UV-filter benzophenone 3. For lead, environmental burden of disease (EBoD) calculations are included. The work on these compounds/compound groups is summarised in this deliverable. The complete RA reports for most of these are included in an annex¹, the rest will be published as scientific journal articles. In addition, the results and more in-depth conclusions based on the work performed in task 5.3 will be included in a scientific manuscript, aiming to provide guidance and examples to (regulatory) risk assessors on the inclusion of HBM data in RA (Santonen et al. in preparation).

It should be noted that the RA/EBoD work presented here is not intended to have regulatory implications. It represents example RAs, illustrating how HBM can be used in RA. However, since newly generated HBM data has been used in many of them, the results can also be useful for raising awareness regarding possibly needed policy actions.

¹ Annex to the Deliverable Report D5.11: Human biomonitoring in risk assessment: 4th set of examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals. Available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6980133>

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5 Approaches used to include HBM data into risk assessment

The overall approach used for RA and EBoD is described below. Full HIA were not made, but EBoD calculations were made for lead, expressed as disability-adjusted life years (DALYs).

The general approach followed in the RA and EBoD calculations was:

1. Identification of the existing RAs for the substance
2. Identification of existing biological guidance values (for the occupational area: limit values) for internal exposure. If not available, identification of existing health-based limit or guidance values for external exposure.
3. Identification of relevant biomonitoring data to be used in RA
4. If there were no existing health-based guidance values (or limit values) for internal exposure, identification of approaches for reverse/forward calculation from health-based external limit or guidance values, e.g. the use of PBPK modelling or mass-balance approach based on one-compartment modelling
5. Performance of RA or EBoD calculations based on HBM data
6. Analysis of benefits and challenges (including uncertainties) of the use of HBM in RA, when compared to the use of external exposure data, and answering the relevant policy questions based on the results.

When human biomonitoring guidance values (HBM-GVs) derived within HBM4EU were available, they were used in the RAs. If they were not available, different approaches were used, depending on the available data, for estimating external intake from biomarker levels or for converting external intake into biomarker levels (reverse or forward calculation, respectively), as described briefly in Table 1.

HBM data were acquired either from published literature or from the HBM4EU aligned studies (Table 1). In some cases, also data originating from the participating institutions' own databases were included. The HBM4EU aligned studies were a survey aimed at collecting HBM samples and data as harmonised as possible from (national) studies, in order to derive current internal exposure data from the European population/citizens across a geographic spread. The HBM4EU aligned studies were conducted under task 8.1 (HBM4EU Deliverable reports D8.1 and D8.8) and task 9.5, and data were further harmonized, transformed and statistically analysed in task 10.6 (HBM4EU Deliverable report D10.12, Gilles et al. 2021, Gilles et al. in preparation). Unless stated otherwise, aggregated data were received from WP10 for the RAs in task 5.3.

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Table 1: Summary of the substances included in the RAs, and general information on the basis for the exposure and hazard assessments

Substance Group	Specific substances included in the RA	Population covered	Exposure assessment: HBM exposure data used	Hazard assessment: GV used / method for its derivation / other type of method used
Acrylamide	Acrylamide	General (children and adults)	HBM4EU aligned studies (aggregated data), based on the acrylamide urinary metabolite AAMA	Key endpoint: cancer, peripheral neuropathy. RA was based on a BMDL ₁₀ value for neoplastic effects in mice and non-neoplastic effects in rats, derived by EFSA in 2015. Internal and external exposure levels in humans were correlated by the urinary mass balance approach, allometric scaling was done to account for inter-species differences. Linear extrapolation was then performed to estimate cancer risks. For peripheral neuropathy risk of acrylamide, a health-based guidance value was derived and RCRs were calculated.
Aprotic solvents	NMP (1-methylpyrrolidin-2-one), NEP (1-ethylpyrrolidin-2-one), DMF (N,N-dimethylformamide)	General (children, adolescents, young adults)	NMP, NEP human biomonitoring data from Germany (Environmental Specimen Bank and GerES V), DMF: human biomonitoring data from Germany (Environmental Specimen Bank)	Key endpoint: developmental toxicity (NMP and NEP), liver toxicity (DMF); NMP and NEP: HBM-GV _{GenPop} derived within HBM4EU from animal studies; HBM-GV _{GenPop} of 15 mg/L for adolescents and adults and 10 mg/L for children; DMF: HBM-GV _{Workers} derived within HBM4EU from occupational study; a provisional HGM-GV _{workers} of 10 mg/g creatinine (cr) was derived; this was divided by an assessment factor of 10 to consider more sensitive subgroups of the population, yielding a provisional HBM-GV _{GenPop} of 1 mg/g cr for the DMF metabolite AMCC.
Arsenic	iAs, MMA and DMA	General (infants, children, adolescents, adults)	Inorganic As intake calculated from food consumption compared to data retrieved from urinary excretion of iAs, MMA and DMA from literature and HBM4EU	Key endpoint: lung, bladder and skin cancer. RA based on BMDL 0.5 = 3.0 µg/kg bw per day and cancer slope of 1.7/1000 for 1 µg iAs/kg bw per day

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Substance Group	Specific substances included in the RA	Population covered	Exposure assessment: HBM exposure data used	Hazard assessment: GV used / method for its derivation / other type of method used
Bisphenols	Bisphenol A (BPA), bisphenol S (BPS)	General (adults)	HBM4EU aligned studies (aggregated data)	Urinary total HBM-GVGenPop of 230 µg/L and 1.0 µg/L were used for BPA and BPS, respectively. The 95th percentiles (P95) reported in the aligned studies were compared to the corresponding HBM-GVGenPop to calculate the corresponding RCRs.
Diisocyanates	MDI (4,4'-methylene diphenyl diisocyanate), TDI (toluene diisocyanate), HDI (hexamethylene diisocyanate)	Workers (adults)	Finnish occupational HBM data from FIOH, metabolites MDA, TDA, HDA	Key endpoint: bronchial hypersensitiveness (BHR). External exposures of MDI and TDI was reconstructed by a developed PBPK method, and HDI by a published correlation equation. In the risk assessment, BHR risk was assessed based on external NCO air concentration reconstructed from urinary diamine levels by using RAC dose-response (2020).
Flame retardants	tris (2-chloroethyl) phosphate (TCEP), tris (chloropropyl) phosphate (TCIPP), tris (1,3-dichloro-2-propyl) phosphate (TDCIPP)	General (children)	HBM4EU aligned studies (aggregated data), based on the urinary metabolite bis (2-chloroethyl) phosphate (BCEP), bis (1-chloro-2-propyl) phosphate (BCIPP) and bis(1,3-dichloro-2-propyl) phosphate) (BDCIPP)	Key endpoint: kidney toxicity. Several HBGV were available and used as minimal risk level and Reference doses for risk assessment. These were: 0.2 mg/kg bw /d for TCEP and TDCIPP (ATSDR), p-RfD of 0.007mg/ kg bw/d for TCEP (US-EPA), RfD of 80 µg/kg bw/d (TCIPP), 22 µg/kg bw/d (TCEP) and 15 µg/kg bw/d (TDCIPP) (Ali et al. 2012). We estimated by reverse dosimetry the daily intake of TCEP, TCIPP and TDCIPP for children using HBM data. For estimating the dietary exposure, a deterministic approach was chosen. The occurrence data of selected food categories were used from a published Belgium food basket study.

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Substance Group	Specific substances included in the RA	Population covered	Exposure assessment: HBM exposure data used	Hazard assessment: GV used / method for its derivation / other type of method used
Lead	Lead	General (infants, children, adolescents, adults)	Existing aggregated data from the HBM4EU repository, based on blood lead levels (BLL), Slovenian HBM data and data retrieved from literature	<p>Key endpoint - children/adolescents: DALYs for developmental neurotoxicity (lost cognitive development), based on a log-linear relationship between BLL and total numbers of Full-Scale IQ points (FSIQ) loss attributable to BLL above 20 µg/L. Sensitivity analysis (considering no threshold in Pb exposure) included all ranges of BLL.</p> <p>Key endpoint - adults: DALYs for premature mortality (all causes of deaths, ICD-10 code I to XX; adults above 20 years), using dose-response relationship and corresponding hazard ratios (relative risk) for BLL above 10 µg/L. The DALYs were presented in absolute numbers and per 100000. In the SLO case, DALYs were presented also as a mean and 95% confidence interval.</p>
Mercury	Methylmercury	General (children and women of childbearing age)	Data retrieved from literature (blood and hair mercury levels). Different studies and DEMOCOPHES	<p>Key endpoint: neurotoxicity. RA approximation based on EFSA (2012) approach. Exposure levels (mercury in hair) were compared to tolerable week intake of 1.3 µg/kg b.w established by EFSA (equivalent to a TDI of 0.19 µg/kg b.w/d, which corresponds to hair levels of 1.9 µg/g).</p> <p>Key endpoint: neurotoxicity. RA based on approach for non-cancer effects using hazard quotients (HQ). HQ were calculated as the ratio of the biomarker concentration to the HBM guidance value for mercury. Two HBM guidance values were used: HBM-I of 5 µg/L in blood described by the German HBM Commission (Schulz et al., 2007) and the preliminary HBM-GV_{GenPop} of 7.2 µg /L in blood provided by HBM4EU WP5 task 5.2 (Dossier on this was not yet completed at the time of the evaluation).</p>

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Substance Group	Specific substances included in the RA	Population covered	Exposure assessment: HBM exposure data used	Hazard assessment: GV used / method for its derivation / other type of method used
Mycotoxins	Deoxynivalenol (DON)	General (children, adolescents, adults)	Data retrieved from literature HBM4EU aligned studies (aggregated data) based on total urinary deoxynivalenol	Key endpoint: reduced body weight gain in experimental animals as the critical chronic effect for human risk assessment. HBGV: Tolerable Daily Intake (1 µg/kg bw/day, DON) and Human Biomonitoring Guidance Value (23 µg/L total urinary DON).
PAHs	1-hydroxypyrene (1-OHPyr) as surrogate for PAH4 (BaA, BbF, BaP, CHR)	General (adults)	HBM4EU aligned studies (aggregated data), based on urinary concentrations	Key endpoint: excess lifetime cancer risk (ELCR). Estimation of intake levels of the main carcinogenic PAHs based on the exposure reconstruction using the available HBM data on urinary 1-OHPyr and translation of this intake into ELCR for the PAH4. ELCR estimate was based on the benchmark dose lower confidence limit (BMDL10) derived by EFSA (2008).
Pesticides: chlorpyrifos	chlorpyrifos and chlorpyrifos-methyl	General (adults and children)	HBM4EU aligned studies (aggregated data) based on U-TCPy levels	Different endpoints covered: the overall PoD was based on developmental neurotoxicity covering the long-term and maternal NOAEL, the short-term NOAEL for red blood cells AChE, and the carcinogenicity NOAEL. HBM-PoDs were estimated using the urinary mass balance approach and compared to U-TCPy levels observed in the HBM4EU aligned studies. MoE approach was used to assess the risk. Acceptable MoE depended on the endpoint and on the confidence related to the PoD. Depending on MoE, risks were graded ranging from very low risk to confirmed concern (from green to red colour codes).

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Substance Group	Specific substances included in the RA	Population covered	Exposure assessment: HBM exposure data used	Hazard assessment: GV used / method for its derivation / other type of method used
Pesticides: pyrethroid mixture	Bifenthrin, Cyfluthrin, Cypermethrin, Deltamethrin, Etofenprox, Fenpropathrin, Fenvalerate, λ-Cyhalothrin, Permethrin, Tau-fluvalinate	General (adults and children)	HBM4EU aligned studies (aggregated data), based on urinary levels of - CIF3CA, trans-CDCA, 3-PBA, 4-F3PBA, cis DCCA, trans DCCA, DBCA	Key endpoint: neurotoxicity/developmental neurotoxicity. For cyfluthrin and deltamethrin, HBM-GVs were used in the RA. For the other pyrethroids and for the general pyrethroid biomarker (3-PBA), a provisional HBM-GV was derived based on an established ADI. First tier RA of pyrethroid mixtures was based on the 3-PBA, for which a conservative provisional HBM screening value was derived. This was refined by using data on specific biomarkers to identify potential contribution of the specific pyrethroids on the total risk.
PFAS mixture	PFBS, PFHxS, PFHpS, PFOS, PFHxA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnDA, PFDoDA	General (teenagers)	HBM4EU aligned studies (individual data), based on plasma/serum concentrations	Key endpoints: immunotoxicity, birth weight reduction. Mixture risk assessment (MRA) for PFASs was performed based on the Relative Potency Factor (RPF) approach, the Hazard Index (HI) approach, and the sum value approach of the European Food Safety Agency (EFSA). For the HI approach, human internal exposures (presented as median or geometric mean serum concentration per cohort) associated with a given effect on immunotoxicity or birth weight reduction were used as PoD. The EFSA TWI, based on a BMDL10 for immune suppression in children, allows to be interpreted at blood serum level, and was used as HBGV in the RPF approach and EFSA sum value approach.
UV filters	Benzophenone-3	General (teenagers – adults)	HBM4EU aligned studies, aggregated data, creatinine corrected urine concentrations	Key endpoint: endocrine disruption. No HBGV has been derived within HBM4EU. A provisional HBM-GV of 340 µg/g creatinine was used based on reduction of the number of spermatocytes per seminiferous tubule in offspring. The POD was the NOAEL of 67.9 mg/kg bw/day from the most recent SCCS opinion.

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6 Summaries of the risk and environmental burden of disease assessments

In this chapter, short summaries of the RAs, EBoD calculations and their main conclusions are provided. The full risk assessments with more detailed information are included in the annex¹, or will be published in scientific journals, as referenced below.

6.1 Acrylamide

Acrylamide is an organic compound produced for different uses in the chemicals industry. It is also formed, when certain foods are prepared at temperatures above 120 °C in the absence of moisture. Acrylamide is detected in numerous baked or fried carbohydrate-rich foods, including frequently consumed foods in all population groups. In addition, acrylamide is present in tobacco smoke.

Acrylamide has been shown to have neurotoxic, carcinogenic, genotoxic and mutagenic effects (Muta. 1B, H340, Carc. 1B, H350 and STOT RE 1, H372** according to the Classification, Labelling and Packaging (CLP) regulation). It also has possible/suspected immunotoxic and developmental toxic effects, and adverse effects on the reproductive function in males (Repr. 2, H361f*** CLP classification). Biomarkers for internal exposure to acrylamide have been established, including urinary metabolites of acrylamide and its main metabolite glycidamide (GA), acrylamide mercapturic acid (AAMA) and glycidamide mercapturic acid (GAMA), and haemoglobin adducts (Hb-AA).

Here, the hazard assessment of acrylamide was performed by summarizing available data from existing risk assessments (annex¹ above). In the acrylamide risk assessment by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA 2015a), it was concluded that acrylamide potentially increases the risk of developing cancer in all age groups of the general population, since the main exposure to acrylamide happens via dietary intake. EFSA (2015a) derived for acrylamide a Benchmark Dose Lower Confidence Limit (BMDL₁₀) of 0.17 mg/kg bw/d based on neoplastic effects in mice, and a BMDL₁₀ of 0.43 mg/kg bw/day based on peripheral neuropathy in rats.

Biomonitoring data from the HBM4EU aligned studies was used for cancer risk assessment of acrylamide, by utilizing the urinary mass balance approach, previously used by Hays and Aylward (2008), to derive biomonitoring equivalent (BE) for acrylamide but using EFSA BMDL₁₀ as a starting point. Acrylamide intake was estimated based on the acrylamide urinary metabolite AAMA, using default bodyweight (30 kg for children, 70 kg for adults) and 24h urine excretion values (0.66 L for children, 1.7 L for adults) for the different population groups. Allometric scaling of BMDL₁₀ dose level of 0.17 mg/kg bw/d from mice to human was made using a default value of 4, which provided a point of departure (POD) for 10 % increase in tumour risk for humans at 42.5 µg/kg bw/d. This was calculated to correspond 2880 µg/L of urinary AAMA in a 70 kg adult (urinary volume of 1.7 L in 24 h). From this, a linear extrapolation to zero risk was performed. EFSA (2015a) proposed also a BMDL₁₀ for non-neoplastic endpoints, 0.43 mg/kg bw/day based on peripheral neuropathy in rats. A health-based guidance value of 0.0043 mg/kg bw/d was derived for peripheral neuropathy by using an assessment factor of 100 to account for uncertainties.

Geometric mean urinary AAMA concentrations in the HBM4EU aligned studies were in the range of 50–70 µg/L in children and 20-100 µg/L in adults. In previously published studies with general population, the corresponding range has been 30–73 µg/L. According to our cancer risk assessment, an acrylamide tumour risk of 1 : 1 000 at 0.425 µg/kg bw/d corresponding 28.8 µg/L of AAMA (in 70 kg adult) was estimated. This means that acrylamide cancer risk for children varied

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from 1:570 to 1:464 and in adults from 1:1384 to 1:288, when biomonitoring data from HBM4EU aligned studies were used as a starting point. These risks correspond to mean acrylamide intakes of 0.75–0.92 µg/kg bw/d in children and 0.31–1.47 µg/kg bw/d in adults, respectively. These levels are in line with the EFSA estimates on acrylamide intake via food (mean intake 0.4–1.9 µg/kg bw/d). Peripheral neuropathy risk was assessed by using the same urinary AAMA data from the aligned studies. RCRs were calculated for children and adults. In general, acrylamide levels were below the defined guidance value 4.3 µg/kg bw/d. However, at 95th percentile of urinary AAMA levels, there were two aligned studies performed with adults giving RCR values of 1.05 (INSEF-ExQAP, Portugal) and 1.75 (ESTEBAN, France), indicating increased risk for peripheral neuropathy.

This risk assessment contains several notable uncertainties. A clear threshold value for cancer risk cannot be established for genotoxic and mutagenic properties of acrylamide. Therefore, the cancer risk assessment is based on a linear extrapolation, which is likely to overestimate the risk at low exposure levels. In addition, cancer risk for humans was based on the most sensitive tumour type (Hardenian gland tumours) in mice, which also might result in overestimation of risk. Use of BMDL₁₀ instead of BMD₁₀ brings some additional conservativeness to the assessment. Uncertainties of peripheral neuropathy risk assessment are related to species differences and assessment factor for deriving a health-based guidance value. There is evidence of endogenous acrylamide formation (0.2-0.4 µg/kg bw/d) in humans, which also cause some uncertainty to human biomonitoring (HBM) based risk assessment. This is, however, estimated to represent lower uncertainty than uncertainties related to linear extrapolation of cancer risk levels from animal studies. In addition, individual variability of acrylamide metabolism can have influence on the HBM levels of acrylamide metabolites.

Monitoring of carcinogenic, mutagenic, and neurotoxic acrylamide is necessary to assess the exposure in the general population in EU. Consumption of roasted or baked starch-based foods and tobacco smoking have been associated with increased acrylamide exposure levels. The acrylamide exposure reduction lays mainly in personal choices regarding smoking and diet. In addition, efforts in non-smoking regulations and support for smoking cessation are important.

6.2 Aprotic solvents

Because of the toxicological profile, a risk assessment for the four aprotic solvents N-methyl pyrrolidone (NMP), N-ethyl pyrrolidone (NEP), N,N-dimethylacetamide (DMAC) and N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF) was planned to be done for all 4 substances. These solvents have a similar toxicological profile and a harmonised classification for reproductive toxicity under the CLP regulation (Repr. 1B). Due to their wide use and high production volume in Europe, a high frequency of exposure is expected.

Even though these substances are of high toxicological concern, a literature search revealed the scarcity of HBM data for these substances for the European population. For DMAC, data could only be found for highly exposed workers. For DMF, samples from the German Environmental Specimen Bank (ESB) were analysed for the metabolite AMCC for the years 2000 to 2021 (data unpublished). Additionally, some data are available from the control group in an occupational study from Germany (Kilo et al., 2016).

As described in more detail in the full RA report (annex¹ above), for NMP and NEP, exposure data are available from two studies conducted in Germany. These include data from the ESB taken from 1991 to 2014 (Ulrich et al., 2018) and data from the German Environmental Survey of Children and Adolescents V (GerES V) (Schmied-Tobies et al., 2021). The data of the two studies were taken as the basis for the risk assessment for NMP and NEP.

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The samples from the ESB allowed investigation of time trends for NMP, NEP and DMF.

Within HBM4EU, human biomonitoring guidance values for the general population (HBM-GV_{GenPop}) have been derived for NMP and NEP. For children, this value is 10 mg/L for both NMP and NEP. For adolescents and adults, an HBM-GV_{GenPop} of 15 mg/L has been derived both for NMP and NEP. For DMF, a provisional HBM-GV_{Workers} of 10 mg/g creatinine has been derived for the metabolite AMCC. For the purpose of this risk assessment, this value was adjusted to a provisional HBM-GV_{GenPop} of 1 mg/g creatinine for a comparison with the data from ESB. The key steps of the derivation of these values are presented in the full RA report.

Also the key exposure data from the studies from Germany are presented and compared.

A comparison of the exposure data with the newly derived HBM-GV_{GenPop} showed that exposure for adults (ESB), children (GerES V) and adolescents (GerES V) is well below the guidance values both for NMP and NEP. Maximum values of the studies were a factor of 4.7 to 10 lower than the corresponding HBM-GV_{GenPop} values. The maximum value found in the data from ESB for the DMF metabolite AMCC was a factor of 2.5 lower than the provisional HBM-GV_{GenPop} of 1 mg/g creatinine.

Even when considering the combined exposure to NMP and NEP, the values are not exceeded. The calculated hazard index (HI) was well below 1 in all cases considered (i.e., children, adolescents and adults) with maximum HI values of 0.3, indicating that there was no exceedance of the HBM-GVs. For young adults, the HI was calculated for the combined exposure to NMP, NEP and DMF resulting in a maximum HI value of 0.6. However, a possible combined exposure with other reprotoxic substances present in the environment should be considered in “real-life-situations”, since these might increase the risk for common effects (Kortenkamp and Faust, 2018).

The high percentage of values above the limit of quantification in the two studies from Germany, and the newly analysed samples for the DMF metabolite, clearly shows that the investigated population was exposed to NMP, NEP and DMF.

The analysis of time trends of NMP and NEP exposure (years 1991-2014) revealed a continuous exposure to both NMP and NEP over the time span investigated. For DMF (years 2000-2021) a > 50% decrease of AMCC concentrations could be observed for the time span investigated.

The analysis of the data from the GerES V study showed that for NMP, the highest exposure was found in young children, but exposure pathways could not be revealed. Exposure to NEP was highest in adolescents and participants with low socio-economic status or migration backgrounds. Associations to usage of personal care products suggested that the choice of products had a distinct impact on NEP exposure.

The original goal of including also DMAC was not realised, due to a lack of HBM data for the general population. Therefore, monitoring for DMAC metabolites in the European population is highly recommended, including susceptible subpopulations to broaden the database. The sources of exposure for the aprotic solvents need to be further investigated and clarified.

6.3 Arsenic

As described in more detail in the full RA report (annex¹ above), recent work related to background levels of inorganic arsenic (iAs) in food, drinking water and environment in the European Union (EU) was summarized; most data included are from studies from 2000 until 2020. Exposure of different population groups was calculated by combining intake and iAs concentrations of food items to obtain daily doses. Conservative approach was used for iAs bioavailability - taken as 100%. Additionally, HBM studies were gathered and iAs daily doses were calculated from urine iAs

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metabolites by reverse daily dose calculation. Both daily iAs dose estimates were used for the assessment of cancer risks – based on dose-response relationship proposed by JEFCA (2011) and ECHA (2013). Uncertainties and limitations of such risk assessment were discussed along with the relevance of the findings in the context of the incidence of selected endpoints (i.e., lung cancer) in the entire general population in the EU. Throughout the text, food intake is used as synonym for food and drinking water intake.

Current exposure of the average EU population to arsenic from drinking water is low due to the limited presence of iAs in drinking water: GM 0.19 µg L⁻¹, P75 0.47 µg L⁻¹, 99 % of samples below the maximum permissible value of 10 µg L⁻¹ in EU (Banks et al. 2015). The main source of iAs is diet, especially rice and other cereals and seafood.

Average exposure levels (daily doses) calculated from food intake and iAs concentrations in food in our study were in the range of 0.07 to 0.20 µg kg⁻¹ bw/day for seven age-stratified population groups (from toddlers to very elderly) and P95 levels lay between 0.19 and 0.64 µg kg⁻¹ bw/day.

In scientific literature and within this project, we identified 28 sets of HBM data on arsenic speciation in the urine of different population groups in the EU, including from 11 to 1737 participants exposed to “normal” levels of iAs. An estimated daily dose of iAs from these urinary levels (including iAs, monomethylarsonic acid (MMA) and dimethylarsinic acid (DMA)) was re-calculated according to Hays et al. (2010), who assumed the linear relationship between the steady-state concentration of arsenic in urine and a daily dose of iAs. On average, estimated daily dose was 0.16 ± 0.07 µg kg⁻¹ bw/day (average of geometric means) and average of P95 was 0.48 ± 0.19 µg kg⁻¹ bw/day, both agreeing well with daily dose calculated from food intake for children, adolescents and adults.

Multiplication of estimated daily dose of iAs from HBM studies (0.16 µg kg⁻¹ bw/day) with a proposed lifetime excess lung cancer risk of 1.7 x 10⁻³ per 1 µg kg⁻¹ bw/day gave an excess lifetime cancer risk of 2.7 x 10⁻⁴ (multiplication of standard deviation was not done since it does not represent the actual dispersion or uncertainty of the values used). Justification of assumptions, necessary to assure the credibility of such calculation, was beyond the scope of this work, therefore, the calculated value must be interpreted with caution. Since the risk assessment is based on the assumption of the linear relationship between the exposure and cancer risk, this approach can be considered as conservative, overestimating the risk especially at low exposure levels. This needs to be considered when using these results.

In addition to the uncertainties related to the dose-response of arsenic-caused-cancer (linear versus non-linear response), especially at low exposure levels there are additional uncertainties, specific for the use of HBM data. These include:

- representativeness of populations and applicability of epidemiological data
- overestimation of iAs exposure due to the widespread presence of DMA in food,
- analytical challenges related to speciation of As species
- inter-individual differences, including individual lifestyle and susceptibility factors

6.4 Bisphenols

A bisphenols risk assessment was previously performed and reported in the HBM4EU Deliverable report D5.8, namely for bisphenol A (BPA) and S (BPS), for which sufficient HBM data were available from the literature, and for which HBM-GVs had been derived in Task 5.2.

Overall, there was a clear difference between risk assessment performed for BPA and BPS exposure, with very low RCR regarding exposure to BPA contrary to those obtained for BPS.

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However, this was due to the fact that the recommended HBM-GVs for BPS are based on endocrine disrupting health effects, occurring in animals at very low doses, contrary to the values calculated for BPA based on the temporary tolerable daily intake (t-TDI) from EFSA (2015b).

Here, the results from the HBM4EU aligned studies were used to update the previous assessment, as described in more detail in the full RA report (annex¹ above).

The outcome of this update, taking into account P95 levels measured in the aligned studies for adults of the general population, remained unchanged with regards to what was concluded in D5.8, and the results were consistent. The difference observed between risk assessment for BPA and BPS exposure remained due to the different choices related to the derivation for the HBM-GV_{GenPop}.

Still, the work performed exemplify how biomonitoring data can be used in the risk assessment of bisphenols, and also challenges and uncertainties related to its use in bisphenols case.

6.5 Diisocyanates

Diisocyanates are a group of chemicals containing two isocyanate functional groups (R-N=C=O, NCO). The most commonly used diisocyanates are 4,4'-methylene diphenyl diisocyanate (MDI), toluene diisocyanate (TDI) and hexamethylene diisocyanate (HDI). Due to the NCO functional groups, all diisocyanates induce similar health effects. Depending on work tasks, workers can be exposed to single diisocyanates, or for example to two different ones. MDI and TDI are classified as suspected of causing cancer (Carc. 2) according to the European Union Classification, Labelling and Packaging (CLP) regulation. In addition, MDI, TDI and HDI are classified as dermal and respiratory sensitizers, and as eye, skin and respiratory irritants. The Risk Assessment Committee (RAC) has identified respiratory health effects (occupational asthma, isocyanate sensitisation and bronchial hyperresponsiveness (BHR)) as the critical endpoints related to diisocyanate exposure. A threshold for BHR or for the development of asthma could not be observed. However, based on the exposure-response studies on hyperresponsiveness or diisocyanate asthma, an occupational exposure limit value (OEL) could be defined as an 8-hour time weighted average (TWA) exposure, based on the NCO groups.

Here, the MDI and TDI external (air) intake levels were estimated from HBM diamine data by a developed PBPK method, as described in the full RA report (annex¹ above). For HDI, exposure reconstruction was based on a published correlation equation (Maitre et al. 1996). Unpublished Finnish HBM data from the Finnish Institute of Occupational Health (FIOH) was the main data source used in the risk assessment, but urinary levels were also compared with published biomonitoring studies. To combine the exposure reconstruction estimates with excess BHR risk estimations, the data points as provided by RAC were used to fit a spline curve. The number of exposed workers to diisocyanates in Finland were estimated from the FIOH FINJEM database (Finnish job-exposure matrix) which covers the major occupational exposures in Finland since 1945 (Kauppinen et al. 2014). Further RAC (2020) estimations for the exposed workers were compared with the total number of Finnish workers in each sector.

In general, excess risk was highest for MDI, especially for the construction sector where we retrieved an excess BHR risk of 3.5%. Also for HDI and TDI, the construction sector pose the highest risk: 2.9% and 3.2% accounting for 165 and 180 excess BHR cases in the Finnish worker population, respectively. For the other sectors (the motor and vehicle repair sector, manufacturing of PUR products and assembling of industrial products) excess risk estimates were between 1.1 – 3.0 %.

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There are several uncertainties in the risk assessment. One issue is the generalizability of the Finnish dataset: in some cases, this data seems to be relatively low in comparison to published data, e.g., for MDI exposure and the manufacturing of PUR products industry. The same counts for TDI exposure in the assembler industry and for HDI in the motor vehicle repair industry. However, results from a recently conducted HBM4EU diisocyanate occupational study indicate that in general exposures were low, often even below the LOD for MDI (HBM4EU Deliverable report D8.13). Furthermore, for HDI, a correlation formula was used here based on air HDI monomer and its urinary metabolite HDA. In workplaces where prepolymers of HDI are used in coating applications, this may result in underestimation of exposure to reactive NCO groups coming from HDI prepolymers, which are not reflected in elevated HDA levels. An advantage of use biomonitoring data over external exposure data is that the HBM includes potential dermal exposure and/or the use of respiratory equipment and as such provides a more realistic exposure dose. For using diisocyanates biomonitoring data we should pay attention to the sensitivity of analysis methods to be able to detect even lower HBM levels of these compounds to efficiently monitor the exposure. The exposure levels of diisocyanates can be anticipated to be lower in the future since the new regulation/restriction in EU (EC 2020/1149) about working with diisocyanates has been put into force. However, there is still a need to monitor the occupational exposure to diisocyanates because a threshold limit value for BHR cannot be established.

6.6 Flame retardants

Due to the extensive usage and chemical properties, organophosphorus flame retardants (OPFR) have been detected in humans and in the environment. Humans are exposed to OPFRs via inhalation of indoor air, dust uptake or dietary uptake through contaminated food and drinking water. Most of the available human biomonitoring studies address OPFR exposure mainly through indoor environment since they are detected in high concentrations in dust and air. Only a few recently published studies also address the dietary exposure of OPFR. In the RA performed (Plichta et al. 2022), we used the HBM data of OPFR to estimate how much the dietary intake contributes to the total exposure.

We estimated, by reverse dosimetry, the daily intake of tris (2-chloroethyl) phosphate (TCEP), tris (1-chloro-2-propyl) phosphate (TCIPP), tris (1,3-dichloro-2-propyl) phosphate (TDCIPP) for children using HBM data from HBM4EU aligned studies with sampling sites in Germany (GerES V (sub, unweighted) study), Belgium (3xG study), Denmark (OCC study), France (Esteban study), Slovenia (SLO CRP study) and Slovakia (PCB cohort study). For estimating the dietary exposure, a deterministic approach was chosen. The occurrence data for certain food categories were used from a published Belgium food basket study. Since the data were left-censored, the Lower bound (LB) - Upper bound (UB) approach was used. The estimated daily intake (EDI) calculated on basis of urine metabolite concentrations ranged from 0.03 to 0.18 µg/kg bw/d for TDCIPP, from 0.05 to 0.17 µg/kg bw/d for TCIPP and from 0.02 to 0.2 µg/kg bw/d for TCEP. Based on food consumption and occurrence data, the estimated dietary intake for TDCIPP ranged from 0.005 to 0.09 µg/kg bw/d, for TCIPP ranged from 0.037 to 0.2 µg/kg bw/d and for TCEP ranged from 0.007 to 0.018 µg/kg bw/d (summarized for all countries). The estimated dietary intake of TDCIPP contributes 11 % to 173 % to the EDI, depending on country and LB-UB scenario. The estimated dietary intake of TCIPP was in all calculations, except in Belgium and France, above 100 % of the EDI, which can be explained by an overestimation regarding the food consumption. In the case of TCEP, it is assumed that the dietary intake ranges from 6 to 57 % of the EDI. As no HBM4EU HBM-GV, neither an HBM-I nor an HBM-II value from the German Human biomonitoring Commission nor a biomonitoring equivalent (BE) were available, a health-based guidance value (HBGV) was derived on the basis of existing external HBGVs. For each study population and exposure scenario (LB -

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UB), the estimated daily intake (EDI) and dietary intake were set in relation to the available HBGV which was derived from external uptake data.

For this risk assessment, the following available HBGVs were used. For TCIPP a reference dose (RfD) of 80 µg/kg bw/d was derived (Ali et al. 2012), where the sensitive endpoint is unknown. In the European Union Risk Assessment Report of TCIPP, a lowest observed adverse effect level (LOAEL) of 52 mg/kg bw/d was derived from a 13-week rat study. The LOAEL was based on the increased liver weight observed in male rats. A minimal margin of safety for repeated dose toxicity of 50 was considered sufficient (European Union 2008). The Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry (ATSDR) derived a minimal risk level for TCEP of 0.2 mg/kg bw/d for chronic exposure (>365 days) based on renal tubule lesions in female rats (ATSDR 2012). The US-EPA derived a chronic provisional reference dose (p-RfD) of 0.007 mg/kg bw/d, based on an increased relative kidney weight (BMDL1SD of 6.9 mg/kg bw/d) (US-EPA, 2009). Another RfD of 22 µg/kg bw/d was derived by Ali et al. (2012), where the sensitive endpoint is increased relative liver and kidney weights in female rats as it was reported by WHO (2004). For TDCIPP, a minimal risk level of 0.2 mg/kg bw/d was derived for chronic exposure (>365 days) based on renal tubule lesions in male rats (ATSDR 2012). A RfD of 15 µg/kg bw/d was derived by Ali et al. (2012), where the sensitive endpoint is increased liver weight in female mice as it was reported by WHO (2004). The EDI and the estimated dietary intake contribute less than 3% to the reference dose (RfD). Therefore, the estimated exposure to OPFRs indicates a minimal health risk based on the current knowledge of available exposure, kinetic and toxicity data. We were able to show that the dietary exposure can have an impact on the general exposure based on our underlying exposure scenarios. It should be noted that the HBGVs used in this assessment are not very recent, bringing uncertainty to the assessment. Some more recent epidemiological studies have suggested carcinogenic, neurotoxic and endocrine disrupting potential, which have not been considered here.

6.7 Lead

The aim of this work (annex¹ above) was to estimate the environmental burden of disease (EBoD), expressed as disability-adjusted life years (DALYs), due to exposure to lead (Pb) in Slovenia (SLO) and selected other EU countries. Data on blood lead levels (BLL) for children and adults at different ages or age groups were obtained from national HBM surveys or similar studies. In Slovenia, these include the DEMOCOPHES and CROME research projects running from 2011–2012 and 2016, respectively; the first part of the national HBM-II survey in 2018 in Mura region, and an annual local HBM in the Meža valley (the Carinthia region), which is well-known Slovenian Pb pollution hot-spot (few centuries long Pb mining and processing). In adults, BLLs were obtained in a nation-wide HBM campaign (HBM-I, 2008–2014), including lactating *primiparous* mothers and men of the same age (18–49 years). In selected EU countries, BLLs were obtained from the HBM4EU repository (available through IPCHEM), including children and adolescents from campaigns in the Czech Republic (CzechHBM-CE_2016), Germany (GerES V (sub, unweighted) in 2014–2017) and Belgium (Flanders; FLEHS IV in 2016–2020), while in adults, these include data from Spain (BIOAMBIENT.ES in 2009–2010), the Czech Republic (CzechHBM-AE_2015) and Belgium (Flanders; FLEHS I in 2004–2005). In children, DALYs were estimated for developmental neurotoxicity (lost cognitive development), based on a log-linear relationship between BLL and total numbers of Full-Scale IQ points (FSIQ) loss attributable to BLL above 20 µg/L. Considering no threshold in Pb exposure, the sensitivity analysis (using all ranges of BLL) was also performed. In adults, DALYs were estimated based on a more recent dose–response relationship and corresponding hazard ratios (relative risk) between BLL above 10 µg/L and premature mortality (all causes of deaths, ICD-10 code I to XX; above 20 years). The DALYs

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were presented in absolute numbers and per 100000. In the SLO case, DALYs were presented also as a mean and 95% confidence interval.

The highest proportion of children, having BLL above 20 µg/L, was identified in the Upper Meža valley hot-spot, e.g., 89% of children, aged 2–4 years, with BLL GM = 47 µg/L, followed by 88% children, aged 8–10 years from the same area, with BLL GM = 41 µg/L. For comparison, in the distant part of the valley, the Lower Meža valley, the proportion of children having BLL > 20 µg/L was 53%, with BLL GM = 34 µg/L. In addition, 10% of children in the Upper Meža valley had BLL above 100 µg/L and some of them also above 200 µg/L. In other SLO HBM studies, a small % (2–14%) had BLL above 20 µg/L with BLL GM between 22–33 µg/L, and none of children had BLL above 100 µg/L. In a recent Belgium (FLEHS IV) HBM study 0% of adolescents of 14–15 years had BLL above 20 µg/L. In the Czech Republic (CzechHBM-CE_2016), 5–17% of children had BLL above 20 µg/L, with BLL GM at 23 and 26 µg/L in age groups 6–11 and 3–5 years, respectively. In Germany (GerES V (sub, unweighted), 2014–2017), the proportions of children with BLL above 20 µg/L were as follows: 7% in the age group 3–5 years, 6% in the age group 6–10 years, 3% in the age group 11–13 years, and 3% in the age group 14–17 years. The corresponding BLL GMs were 25, 23, 22 and 25 µg/L, respectively. Corresponding DALYs in children were the highest in the Meža valley in general, 978–3437 (95%CI: 605–4955) per 100,000 children, which was more than 10-fold higher than in other Slovenian regions in general, 18–26 (95% CI: 11–37). This was also significantly higher than in children in selected EU countries. In the Czech Republic, DALYs were 19 and 127 per 100 000 (considering two age groups), and between 8 and 47 in Germany (considering four age groups). In general, DALYs were higher in younger children of 3–5 years, comparing children of age between 6 and 10 years and adolescents, 11–17 years. It is also obvious from the numerous studies that over time BLLs decreased significantly (e.g., FLEHS IV and GerES V (sub, unweighted)).

In SLO adults, 18–49 years, 98% of participants in the Meža valley had BLL above 10 µg/L, with BLL GM at 28 µg/L. In Slovenia overall, this proportion was 92%, with BLL GM at 19 µg/L, and it was higher in men than in women, 21 and 18 µg/L, respectively. Corresponding DALYs were 464 (95%CI: 244–661) per 100,000 adults in the Meža valley versus 311 (95% CI: 161–450) in Slovenia overall. Regarding gender, DALYs were 348 (95%CI: 181–502) and 276 (95%CI: 142–399) per 100 000 in men and women, respectively. In Belgium (FLEHS I), 100% of participants of 40–59 years had BLL above 10 µg/L with BLL GM at 37 µg/L and corresponding DALYs was calculated at 733. In two age groups of adults in Spanish HBM, 97% of participants of 20–39 years had BLL above 10 µg/L with BLL GM at 21 µg/L, and 99% of participants of 40–59 years had BLL above 10 µg/L with BLL GM at 28 µg/L. Corresponding DALYs were 314 and 427, respectively. In two age groups of Czech's adults, 75% of participants of 20–39 years had BLL above 10 µg/L with BLL GM at 19 µg/L, while in the elder group of 40–59 years, 86% had BLL above 10 µg/L with BLL GM at 23 µg/L. The corresponding DALYs were 385 and 546, respectively. In general, higher DALYs were calculated in older adults, and based on older HBM surveys (Belgium).

These estimates, however, should only be compared with caution, because of different time periods, differences in age groups of participants, and other potential differences, that could not be considered. These include also some uncertainties related to dose response relationship used in the calculations. More studies are also needed to confirm these dose-responses. Nevertheless, the results in this report can be considered as important, achieving one of the common goals of HBM4EU, e.g., harmonisation of the HBM protocols and consequently better understanding and comparison of human exposure and health outcomes at the EU level. New data on HBM at EU level, however, will certainly contribute significantly to a more reliable assessment of the EBoD.

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6.8 Mercury and its organic compounds

Mercury (Hg) is a global environmental pollutant with toxicity threatening human and wildlife health. Among its species, methylmercury (MeHg) is the greatest cause of human health concern since it is the most toxic and bioaccumulates and biomagnifies in the food chain. It can cause severe impacts on human health, including irreversible damage to the central nervous system, even at very low levels depending on the age exposure window. Consequently, MeHg poses a significant risk to foetuses, as it can cross the placenta, and to young children, acting on their developing nervous system. Therefore, women of childbearing age, pregnant women and younger children constitute an especially vulnerable population group, mainly in regions with a seafood-based diet. Additionally, new evidence suggests that the different forms of mercury (MeHg and inorganic Hg) may be associated with cardiovascular and immunotoxicity effects.

In order to estimate the human risk associated with MeHg, a RA was conducted using HBM data (Domínguez-Morueco et al. in preparation), since it is a powerful tool to provide data about chemicals or metabolites in human biological matrices, integrating all possible sources and routes of exposure.

RA of MeHg was conducted based on earlier approaches by EFSA in 2012 and integrating data from European HBM surveys. Children/adolescents from 3 to 17 years old and, women of childbearing age in the range of 18 to 50 years old were identified as relevant population groups for this RA. Two types of MeHg HBM datasets were selected: HBM studies (n= 21) with Hg levels (blood and hair, total Hg and/or MeHg) in the general population in different EU countries and the DEMOCOPHES harmonised study as reference (hair) (total Hg) in children/mothers in 17 EU countries. Since mercury in hair is mainly (89-91%) in the form of MeHg (Cernichiari et al., 1995, Miklavcic et al., 2011), to transform mercury levels in hair to their equivalent in blood, an updated hair to blood ratio of 280 described by Esteban et al., 2021 was applied for those studies with data (geometric mean (GM) and/or 95th percentile (P95)) of total Hg in hair. In this sense, a total of 6 case-studies were suggested as RA strategies for each group identified. These case-studies were based on estimations of the fraction of children/adolescents and women from the EU general population exceeding the TWI (or their equivalent to TDI) defined by EFSA in 2012 (case-studies 1 and 2, respectively); and based on estimations of the fraction of children/adolescents and women of childbearing age from the EU general population exceeding the HBM-I blood value established by the German Human Biomonitoring Commission (Hazard Quotient-HQ) (case-studies 3 and 4). In addition, similar calculations but using the preliminary less-restrictive HBM-GV_{GenPop} blood value provided by WP5 task 5.2 were conducted (case-studies 3b and 4b).

The MeHg RA results based on TWI, show that children/adolescents and women of childbearing age hair values (both range of GM and range of P95 in selected HBM studies and GM and P95 in DEMOCOPHES) are below 1.9 µg/g, therefore in general the European population does not exceed the daily average/intake dose for MeHg/Hg.

Regarding the results based on the use of the HBM-I through HQ calculations, it was observed that for both children/adolescents and women of childbearing age, the risk varies across different EU countries and that some EU areas are close to or exceeding the exposure guidance values. This is the case of Spain and Portugal, which showed highest HQ, probably due to their higher seafood consumption frequency. However, when the assessment was conducted using the HBM-GV_{GenPop}, the EU population (children/adolescents and women of childbearing age) did not overall exceed the HQ value of 1, thus indicating no risk of adverse health effects due to MeHg exposure and only two studies were over the HBM-GV_{GenPop}. The use of a less restrictive HBM-GV reduces the risk

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characterisation ratio, the Hazard Quotient-HQ and therefore the risk of adverse health effects for some of the studies.

A possible underestimation was identified in our assessment since DEMOCOPHES, albeit being a harmonised study, did not include data from other European countries with also high fish consumption such as France, Italy, Greece or Iceland. For this reason, further RA refinement is needed with harmonized and widespread HBM data to account for differences in European exposure.

6.9 Mycotoxins

Mycotoxins are a group of chemical food contaminants, including aflatoxins, deoxynivalenol, zearalenone, patulin, fumonisins, among others. These compounds are secondary metabolites of fungi that contaminate food commodities at different stages of the food chain, namely in the production, harvest, storage, and processing. Mycotoxins are relevant in a public health perspective due to their potential to have several toxic effects in humans such as carcinogenic, genotoxic, teratogenic, estrogenic, and immunomodulatory effects. After a prioritisation process, deoxynivalenol and fumonisin B₁ were included in the 2nd set of substances prioritised under HBM4EU. Fumonisin B₁ was not included in the present RA because there is very limited human biomonitoring data to support its exposure assessment. This is due to its low urinary recovery and high inter-individual variability in absorption and excretion, which leads to a high uncertainty, not allowing an accurate risk characterization. As such, the RA pertained only to deoxynivalenol (DON).

The general aim of the RA was to assess the risk associated to human exposure to DON, in populations from different European countries or regions based both on published human biomonitoring data (annex¹ above) and on the new data generated for the adult population in the context of the aligned studies developed across Europe (NIOM_POLAES, UI_DIET_HBM, UBA_ESB and LNS_Oriscav-Lux2 studies). For both databases, two approaches were followed, *i*) using human biomonitoring data and estimating the external exposure (Probable Daily Intake, PDI) through reverse dosimetry and thereafter, determining the hazard quotient through comparison with the available external health-based guidance value, and *ii*) comparing the human biomonitoring data with the HBM-GV determined for DON in the scope of the work developed under Task 5.2. Results for risk characterization regarding data obtained in the HBM4EU aligned studies will be further detailed in a future publication under HBM4EU (Namorado et al. in preparation).

The results showed that exposure to DON in the European population is generalised, affecting different age groups of the population. Children and pregnant women, which are traditionally considered vulnerable population groups, presented the highest risk. The children group deserves particular attention, considering the associated vulnerability and the potential long-term consequences that are difficult to predict. The human biomonitoring guidance value for DON derived under task 5.2 of the HBM4EU project allowed for the first time, to assess the risk of DON based on exposure biomarkers and an HBM-GV. Results from the aligned study conducted in adult population from Poland and Luxembourg showed that the highest percentiles of exposure (P90 and P95) represented a potential health concern since the hazard quotient determined is above one. However, the mean and median levels of exposure were considered as not representing a concern for health. Results obtained from the aligned studies conducted in Iceland and Germany revealed an exposure to DON that does not represent a health concern.

The use of HBM data for mycotoxins implies an extensive knowledge of metabolism but there are still some gaps regarding mycotoxins' toxicokinetic data that may hamper a proper risk

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assessment. If developing a risk assessment for regulatory purposes, all these aspects are important to be considered and assume a higher relevance. The establishment of an HBM-GV is of major relevance for performing a more accurate risk characterization, allowing a direct comparison of exposure with a reference value, and reducing the uncertainty in estimates. However, regarding compounds for which a reduced knowledge on metabolism is available, the issue of uncertainty in estimates remains and the limitations of the HBM-GV should be described in detail.

Considering the present RA, the use of HBM data for risk assessment encompasses some limitations that are related with the use of data published in several scientific articles, non-harmonized sample collection and criteria for left-censored data. These limitations could be overcome in a near future by developing of guidance for setting-up biomonitoring campaigns that would allow a proper comparison of exposure among studies whole lowering the uncertainties that affect risk assessment.

6.10 PAHs

Considering the new HBM data on polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) exposure for the general population (urinary level of 1-OHPyr), provided recently by the HBM4EU aligned studies, the aim of the present work was to update the PAHs risk assessment previously performed within D5.5 that was based on published data. Here, the aligned study cohorts included adults from the general population from France (A_ANSP_ESTEBAN), Czech Republic (A_MU_(C)ELSPAC), Croatia (A_CIPH_HBM in Croatia), Germany (A_UBA_ESB), Iceland (A_UI_DIET_HBM), Luxembourg (A_LNS_Oriscav-Lux2), Poland (A_NIOM_POLAES) and Switzerland (A_SWISS TPH_HBM4EU).

In the present work (annex¹ above), the estimation of the of excess lifetime cancer risk (ELCR) was performed using two stages. In the first stage, the external exposure was reconstructed, i.e. the probable daily intake (PDI) of pyrene was estimated based on HBM data on 1-hydroxypyrene (1-OHPyr) available in the aligned studies. The PDI of pyrene intake levels were then translated into PAH4 (BaA, BbF, BaP, CHR) intake levels based on the assumption that pyrene intake was a surrogate of PAH4. In the second approach, for comparison, PAH4 dietary intake levels were derived from the country specific food residue and the food consumption data, available in the EFSA reports (2008, 2015c). Derived PAH4 intakes were then used as an input to estimate ELCR, using the ECHA-RAC (2018) formula.

The mean intake of PAH4 derived from the EFSA data on the occurrence of PAHs in food was, in general, one order of magnitude higher than that estimated based on exposure reconstruction from the HBM4EU aligned study data (mean values of 1-OHPyr). This was probably due to the conservative nature of the bottom-up approaches based on the EFSA data, compared to the one that was based on HBM data. Consequently, the ELCR estimates based on EFSA's PAH4 intake levels were higher than those calculated from intake levels based on HBM data exposure reconstruction. Thus, EFSA's bottom-up approach may be considered as the worst-case scenario for exposure estimation. The ELCR mean values estimated from HBM data ranged from 3.9×10^{-6} to 3.2×10^{-5} . Considering the indicative tolerable cancer risk level of 10^{-6} for the general population proposed by the European Commission (EC 2001), the ELCR results obtained in the present work were of concern for 4 of the 7 cohorts included in the aligned studies (Luxembourg, France, Czech Rep and Poland), all with ELCR estimation in the 10^{-5} range.

However, it should be noted that for this estimation, the approach used considered only the oral route of exposure, i.e. it assumed that most of the intake occurs by the oral route. Since it is well known that inhalation also contributes to PAHs exposure at a similar proportion (roughly 50%), the ELCR values calculated may underestimate the real cancer risk. Thus, for a more realistic

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estimate, the inhalation route of exposure should be addressed properly in future risk assessment studies. Furthermore, the assumption that the pyrene intake derived from the urinary 1-OHPyr is representative of PAH4 intake should be taken with caution, and also other uncertainties that were not addressed in this work should be considered. As the HBM4EU aligned studies provided data also on other PAHs metabolites, such as 1-hydroxynaphthalene and 9-hydroxyfluorene 4-hydroxyphenanthrene, these might be used in future RA studies to reduce uncertainties and eliminate potential doubts as much as possible. To allow RA based on those metabolites, it is also of the greatest importance to deliver HBGVs for PAHs metabolites that would help to interpret the HBM results in much more reliable health risk context.

It is concluded that the most recent values obtained in the HBM4EU aligned studies showed that the levels of internal exposure of the European adult population were similar to those from previous studies published in the literature. There were no indications that the newly obtained HBM data for 1-OHPyr were substantially lower than the ones previously measured and reported in the open literature. In addition, while comparing the risk estimations with the ones formerly estimated and presented in D5.5, the risk levels now estimated are at the same order of magnitude, with an exception of smokers (10^{-4}), when considering solely oral (dietary) exposure. From the health policies questions perspective, further efforts should be envisaged for reducing intake and potential contamination with PAHs from various sources.

6.11 Pesticides

6.11.1 Chlorpyrifos and chlorpyrifos-methyl

Chlorpyrifos and chlorpyrifos-methyl are organophosphate pesticide active substances extensively used in the EU until the withdrawal of their authorisations in 2020. In 2014, EFSA proposed lowering the acceptable daily intake (ADI), triggering a significant modification of the maximum residue levels (MRLs) in 2016. In 2019, EFSA identified additional concerns, leading to a final decision by European commission (EC) and member states (MS) to withdraw all authorisation by 16 February 2020. This was done with a maximum grace period of 16 April 2020, combined with the reduction of all MRLs to the default value of 0.01 mg/kg by 13 November 2020.

In the EU, consumer exposure has direct links with the applicable MRLs. The HBM4EU aligned studies cover the period between both decisions. The retrospective assessment summarised here provides information on actual risk levels during that period, and additional rationale regarding the links between real exposure and the adopted decisions (Tarazona et al. in preparation).

The hazard assessment was based on the EFSA 2019 conclusion; using the Points of Departure (PoD) proposed in the EFSA list of endpoint for chlorpyrifos, complemented with a literature review on toxicokinetic studies in human volunteers.

The selected marker, TCPy (3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol), is a common metabolite with chlorpyrifos-methyl. The assessment based on chlorpyrifos covers the exposure to both substances.

As in the 2019 assessment an ADI was not established, the risk characterization followed the margin of exposure (MoE) approach. The HBM4EU methodology for setting HBM-GVs (Apel et al. 2020) was adapted for establishing HBM-PoDs, to be used as reference points in the MoE estimations. The first step is similar, human toxicokinetic data is used for selecting the fraction of administered dose expected as urinary metabolite, *F_{ue}*. Chlorpyrifos is nearly completely converted to equimolar amounts of TCPy and alkyl phosphate metabolites; thus, this fraction is directly linked to oral uptake. In a pharmacokinetic study with six human volunteers, the percentage of the administered oral dose recovered in urine as TCP ranged between 49 and 81 percent with an average of 70%; the average has been used for the estimations. The HBGV is

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replaced by the selected PoD. Three PoD values (0.1; 0.3 and 10 mg/kg bw/day) were used, resulting in HBM-PoDs ranging between 1.98 and 198.1 mg/l for adults and 1.32 and 132.07 mg/l for children. The risk characterisation covered the overall risk (OA- based on developmental neurotoxicity, LOAEL), long-term and maternal toxicity (LT), short-term AChE (ST), and carcinogenicity (C).

The interpretation of the MoEs requires specific considerations based on the selected PoD and the associated health concerns. Some are based on the extrapolation factors proposed for the derivation of HBGV (EFSA SC 2012a, ECHA 2012), while others are specifically associated to the assessment of substances with potential genotoxicity concerns (EFSA SC 2012b).

MoE values were estimated for the 50th and 95th percentiles, representing average population and the high exposed group, respectively, as well as for the upper CI of the 95th percentile to cover internal individual variability within the highly exposed group. The values were sorted in four main categories, associated to a colour code:

RED: Confirmed concern: the MoE is lower than the requirements for uncertainty factors in standard assessments, i.e. lower than 100 for the NOAELs, lower than 300 for the LOAEL, and lower than 10000 for the carcinogenicity of genotoxic substances

ORANGE: Possible concern: the MoE is lower than the requirements for uncertainty factors in standard assessments plus the upper range regarding additional considerations for the extrapolation (factor of 10 for NOAEL to LOAEL, and factor of 3 for subacute to subchronic extrapolation)

YELLOW: Concerns cannot be excluded. MoEs higher than those above but not offering an additional margin of 10.

GREEN: Risk cannot be excluded due to the concerns on genotoxicity but is expected to be very low; MOEs providing an additional margin of at least 10 from those of possible or confirmed concern.

HBM exposure data was available from following countries and cohorts:

Adults: PT INSEF, Study CH, IL RAVMABAT, FR ESTEBAN, IS Diet_HBM, DE ESB

Children: FR Esteban, SI SLOCRP, NL SPECIMEN, BE 3xG, CY Organiko, IL RAVMABAT

For children the highest risk levels, reaching red level (confirmed concerns), were observed for Israel and Cyprus. For adults, orange level for MoE based on 95th percentile, were observed for Israel and Portugal. Due to differences in the data sets, only generic comparisons with regulatory decisions can be extracted. The German ESB data provides information for levels in three years, 2015, 2017 and 2020, showing reductions in the exposure levels that could be in principle connected to decisions on authorisations and MRLs. Important differences among EU MSs, all bounded by the same regulatory frame, are observed. In particular, no quantitative estimations can be provided for France, as most of the results were below the limit of detection; the sampling was between 2014 and 2016, and indicates lower exposure levels than in other MSs for sampling conducted after the 2016 MRL revision.

Concerns cannot be excluded (orange level for children in Cyprus, yellow level for all other countries) even for the average population (MoE based on 50th percentiles). It should be noted that at the time of sampling, these two active substances were authorised and marketed in the EU, while now are no longer authorised and all MRLs have been established at the default value. These results from human biomonitoring further support this decision.

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The urinary marker TCPy covers only two closely related active substances, chlorpyrifos and chlorpyrifos-methyl. Thus, it is not relevant, per se, for covering cumulative risk to pesticides mixtures. However, the combination of this specific urinary marker (TCPy) with a second biomarker, based on urinary levels of alkyl phosphate metabolites common to several other pesticides, would allow setting a human biomonitoring program including a screening tier, using markers common to a large number of active substances and a refined tier if the markers for the screening are exceeded. This kind of program would facilitate the implementation and prioritisation of human biomonitoring.

As high variability regarding the exposure and associated risk has been identified within and among the databases, a more in-depth assessment could be relevant in order to identify if the high exposure correspond to chance events or to specific individual patterns or characteristics. In this sense, it is relevant to mention that even with the limited number of human volunteers, high individual variability was observed in the toxicokinetic study.

6.11.2 Pyrethroid mixture

Pyrethroids are a major class of insecticides that are widely used in Europe in agri- and horticulture, but also for biocidal purposes (including household application) and as veterinary drugs. Accordingly, significant human exposure is likely. Regarding toxic mixture effects of pyrethroids on non-target organisms, such as humans, additivity is assumed because of the same or similar (neurotoxic) mode of action.

Pyrethroids are suitable for biomonitoring, since common but also more or less specific metabolites may be readily measured in human urine. In addition, there is toxicokinetic data on the rate of excretion of pyrethroid metabolites, allowing estimation of urinary metabolite levels corresponding to specific external intake levels. This approach has been used to derive HBM guidance values (HBM-GVs) for deltamethrin and cyfluthrin within HBM4EU (HBM4EU Deliverable report D5.12). Additionally, for the purposes of this risk assessment, we derived an HBM screening value for the general pyrethroid metabolite, 3-PBA, and provisional HBM-GVs for the pyrethroids bifenthrin, cypermethrin, etofenprox, fenpropathrin, fenvalerate, λ -cyhalothrin, permethrin and tau-fluvalinate, based on their ADI levels. Selection of these pyrethroids for the current evaluation was made based on their actual use in Europe, taking into account the metabolites measured in the HBM4EU aligned studies.

Since many pyrethroids have the metabolite 3-phenoxybenzoic acid (3-PBA) in common, a conservative (generic) screening value for this substance in urine was established to allow a rough estimate of overall exposure to pyrethroids, with subsequent risk assessment (Tier I assessment). For this purpose, a worst-case calculation was performed, in which the lowest ADI of the various pyrethroids under consideration (i.e. 0.0025 mg/kg bw as derived for lambda-cyhalothrin) and the lowest conversion ratio (i.e., 9% as found with deltamethrin) were used as input parameters. The resulting provisional HBM screening values were 3.25 μ g 3-PBA/L for children and 4.8 μ g/L for adults. If the 95thile in an HBM study is below these levels, no problem with pyrethroid exposure is anticipated in the population under study. Exceedance of the screening value will normally warrant or stipulate further investigations.

For further refinement of the RA, and to provide evidence as to which particular substance a high exposure might be due (Tier II assessment), specific HBM-GVs for individual pyrethroids, if available, were used. Compound-specific HBM-GVs are available for deltamethrin and cyfluthrin, even though the uncertainty regarding the latter seems markedly higher. These HBM-GVs were based on the unique deltamethrin metabolite DBCA and on the cyfluthrin metabolite 4-F3PBA.

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For some other pyrethroid compounds, provisional HBM-GVs were proposed based on metabolites that are not unique, but released only by a small number of parent substances. Depending on the parent, this calculation may give different specific HBM-GVs. For risk assessment, the lowest ones were used under the “worst case” assumption that urinary concentrations were entirely due to previous exposure to the most toxic substance in this group. Thus, the provisional HBM-GV for cypermethrin, based on the metabolite DCCA, covered also exposure to permethrin, cyfluthrin (for which, however, 4-F3PBA may be also used as a suitable marker) and, in principle, the veterinary drug flumethrin. However, they are all of lower chronic toxicity than cypermethrin. Likewise, the provisional HBM-GV for lambda-cyhalothrin, based on CFMP (CIF3CA), may also cover previous exposure to bifenthrin and tefluthrin.

Various pyrethroid metabolites were measured in a number of HBM4EU aligned studies in children in Belgium, Cyprus, France, Israel, Slovenia, and the Netherlands as well as in adults in France, Germany, Israel, and Switzerland. The specific cohorts were:

- Adults: PT INSEF, Study CH, IL RAVMABAT, FR ESTEBAN, IS Diet_HBM, DE ESB
- Children: FR Esteban, SI SLOCRP, NL SPECIMEN, BE 3xG, CY Organiko, IL RAVMABAT

For risk assessment, the risk characterization ratios (RCR) between the 95thile of urine measurements (in µg/L, not adjusted for creatinine) and the provisional “screening” HBM-GV (3-PBA) or the respective compound-specific HBM-GVs were calculated.

Tier I assessment revealed mixed results. Whereas the provisional HBM screening value for adults was not exceeded in any study, RCRs were consistently above 1 for children in all six countries that data is available from. Probabilistic refinement of this data reduced the likelihood of risk in children to a small subgroup in Belgium (about 2%), assuming that exposure was linked to the most toxic pyrethroid, i.e., lambda-cyhalothrin.

In Tier II assessment, all the 95thiles of urinary concentrations in the aligned studies were well below the respective (provisional) HBM-GVs for bifenthrin, cypermethrin, deltamethrin and lambda-cyhalothrin, both in adults and children. Relative high concentrations of cypermethrin in children (up to 25% of HBM-GV) might suggest a need for closer monitoring but could be also explained by parallel exposure to permethrin and cyfluthrin, since both compounds give the same metabolite DCCA. It could not be clarified to which single pyrethroid the increased risk in the subpopulation of Belgian children might be due. It is rather unlikely that lambda-cyhalothrin was the only or predominant source.

On balance, recent HBM data suggest low concern regarding pyrethroid exposure of the general population in Europe, even though a potential risk for some highly exposed children cannot be completely excluded. In addition, there are some uncertainties related to the developmental neurotoxicity, since ADIs given for many pyrethroids are based on neurotoxicity observed in adult experimental animals, which may not sufficiently protect against developmental neurotoxicity during pregnancy/early infancy. Since detailed hazard assessment was not performed, it was not possible to fully address this aspect. However, the scientific and regulatory value of inclusion of HBM data in risk assessment of pesticides was demonstrated and should be expanded to also other groups of pesticides than pyrethroids. A similar approach could be taken for assessing exposure and risk in populations with mainly occupational exposure. Human biomonitoring, in future, may become a powerful tool for realistic exposure estimates and risk assessment of pesticides.

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6.12 PFAS mixture

Perfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) are a highly persistent, mobile, and bioaccumulative class of chemicals, of which emissions into the environment are expected to result in long-lasting contamination with high probability for causing adverse effects to human health and the environment; some of them already at current exposure (body burden) levels. The aim of this study was to refine the mixture risk assessment of PFASs taking three approaches for comparison: the Relative Potency Factor (RPF) approach, the Hazard Index (HI) approach, and the sum value approach of EFSA (HBM4EU Deliverable report D5.8). The latter approach uses the EFSA tolerable weekly intake (TWI) value for the sum of PFOA, PFNA, PFHxS, and PFOS (“EFSA-4”).

Within HBM4EU, one objective was to provide a European-wide, harmonized dataset for human exposure to PFASs. In the HBM4EU aligned studies, HBM datasets for teenagers from nine European countries were obtained with harmonized SOPs and presented in the same way, as to decrease any methodological differences that would affect the comparison between datasets. The human biomonitoring studies were conducted under T8.1 (D8.1 and D8.8) and T9.5, and data were further harmonized, transformed and statistically analysed in T10.6. As a result, a recent, Europe-wide snapshot of exposure to PFASs was obtained. This dataset (N = 1957) served as the basis for the current RA (Bil et al. in preparation).

In a deterministic approach, one usually adds up summary statistics of exposure to each substance (e.g. P50 or P95) in mixture risk assessment. As such, one relies on the assumption that the pairwise correlation among PFAS exposures is 1. However, pairwise correlations among PFAS may vary, and positive correlations are strongly dependent on exposure source(s) (EFSA 2020). Therefore, for the sum value approach and the RPF approach, we used the mixture blood concentrations at the individual level, using the raw exposure data of the PFAS mixtures for each person separately. This means that for the sum value approach, the blood serum or plasma concentration for PFOA, PFNA, PFHxS and PFOS were summed per individual, and the percentiles for the EFSA-4 per country were then used to interpret the risk. For RPF approach, we multiplied the RPF with PFAS blood concentrations to obtain PFOA Equivalents (PEQs) per individual, and then presented the percentiles for the sum PEQs per country to interpret the risk. The risk assessments were subsequently based on P50 and P95 of these distributions. For the HI approach, P50 and P95 values per substance per cohort were used as input for the risk assessment.

The mixture risk assessments illustrate that HBM provides a highly valuable contribution to the assessment of the cumulative risk resulting from exposure to PFASs. It is inherent to HBM to reflect the aggregated exposure from different exposure routes and exposure sources and therefore reflects exposure from all potential sources. It should be mentioned that this current work is a scientific exploration of how to use HBM in risk assessment. This exercise presents several approaches to perform mixture risk assessment for PFASs that are based on pragmatism, and each approach has its strengths, assumptions, uncertainties and flaws. All approaches indicate that PFAS exposure may cause adverse health effects in certain segments of the European population, thereby confirming the conclusion drawn in the recent EFSA scientific opinion.

For future research, we stress the need for improving the analytical methods for biomonitoring and for bringing down the LOD and LOQ. We recommend performing studies that observe paired blood-urine samples to have a better insight into exposure to short-chain PFASs. For a refined mixture risk assessment, taking into account mixture exposure, we recommend considering mixture exposure at the individual level rather than using summary statistics for the summation of exposure to multiple compounds. Furthermore, it is preferable to include exposure and effect data

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in the risk assessment at the individual level. This would solve problems regarding difficulties in point-of-departure setting. We recommend validating relative potencies of PFASs for other effects, sex, life-stages, and species, and in particular for critical effects such as immune effects. In line with this, we recommend – if feasible - to develop a human-based in vitro/ex vivo model for immunotoxicity that can mimic the in vivo response. And lastly, we advise, complementary to this, to investigate mode(s) of action and adverse outcome pathways for PFASs to overcome data gaps and to shed light on species concordance.

6.13 UV-filter benzophenone-3

Benzophenone-3 (BP-3) is a UV-filter that is widely applied in a variety of consumer products, principally sunscreens and other cosmetic products, and in lower amounts in paints and coatings. Due to concerns on the endocrine disruptive properties of BP-3, there is a consumer concern for a possible risk through the use of BP-3 containing products.

Under the scope of the HBM4EU project, a risk assessment was performed of BP-3 based on human biomonitoring data (annex¹ above). In the previous deliverable, the biomonitoring data from three literature studies performed in the period 2010-2013 was used (Annex in the Deliverable Report D5.8). This risk assessment found an increased risk for the highly exposed population, but not for typical exposure. After this study, new HBM measurements were performed within the HBM4EU aligned studies, including data on BP-3, with a sampling period ranging from 2014-2018. This RA provides an update of the risk assessment with this new data. In addition, the point of departure (POD) was updated in line with the 2021 Scientific Committee for Consumer Safety (SCCS) opinion. This resulted in the use of a lower POD, but also a lower assessment factor due to the difference in endpoint. As the difference in the resulting provisional HBM guidance value was relatively small (less than 3-fold decrease), the outcome of the risk assessment on the studies from literature stayed essentially the same.

Six of the aligned studies conducted from 2014 to 2018 within HBM4EU performed new measurements of benzophenones, including BP-3. The question was whether there would be any change in the exposure, in particular due to the lower maximum allowed concentration of BP-3 in sunscreen products since 2017. The outcome of the new risk assessment showed that indeed the P50 and P95 are lower in the more recent measurements. Of the six new studies the highest Risk Characterization Ratio (RCR) at the P95 was 0.2, where it was 1.15 in the previous assessment. However, an important note is that the highest exposed cohort in the previous assessment was not included in the aligned studies, while the other cohorts from literature had similar exposure levels to those in the aligned studies. In general, higher exposure levels were found in woman than in men in the new studies. No clear influence was found of age or sample regime.

This preliminary risk assessment of BP-3 implied that in general there is no risk indicated to the population included in the aligned studies. It also shows that there are notable differences in exposure between groups, with the most highly exposed groups approaching (but not surpassing) the acceptable risk levels for BP-3. This analysis was greatly aided by the HBM4EU aligned studies, which ensured that measurements were performed and analysed in a standardized way that enabled a meaningful comparison. This study notes the value of empirical HBM data and highlights the importance of the HBM4EU initiative in advancing and coordinating biomonitoring research in Europe.

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7 Results in the light of the policy questions

7.1 Acrylamide

Policy question (PQ): Are the exposure levels a concern for health? Is the exposure to acrylamide associated to cancer, neurological alterations and foetal growth in humans? Is the health risk dependent on long term or intermittent exposure to low quantity of acrylamide?

The exposure levels of acrylamide in the HBM4EU aligned studies are similar in the general population as previously reported by EFSA and by published HBM studies. Concerning cancer risk, our risk assessment suggested a clear concern for general population. This is in accordance with the earlier risk assessment by EFSA. Regarding peripheral neuropathy risk, in general acrylamide levels were below the provisional HBM-GV derived. However, at 95th percentile of urinary AAMA levels, there were two aligned studies performed with adults giving RCR values of 1.05 (INSEF-ExQAP, Portugal) and 1.75 (ESTEBAN, France), indicating a concern for peripheral neuropathy. This risk assessment contains several potential uncertainties, which are mainly related to the extrapolation of the risks for humans by using animal data and may lead to overestimation of risk. The association of acrylamide to foetal growth, or the dependence of health risk on long term or intermittent exposure to acrylamide were not considered here.

PQ: Are the health risks dependent on age and gender? Which population groups are more at risk?

Based on this work, it is not possible to identify age or gender dependencies.

Recommendations for the regulatory risk assessment

Continuation of the monitoring of acrylamide is necessary to assess the exposure in the EU general population (EC 2017/2158). Consumption of roasted or baked starch-based foods and tobacco smoking have been associated with increased acrylamide exposure levels. The acrylamide exposure reduction lays mainly in personal choices regarding smoking and diet. In addition, efforts in non-smoking regulations and support for smoking cessation are important.

Future prospects

The continuous monitoring of acrylamide exposure levels in general population is important in the future and should include HBM data from several other European countries. In addition, making general population more aware with information campaign of acrylamide and its sources could reduce the levels.

7.2 Aprotic solvents

Building a picture of internal exposure burden for NMP and NEP (eventually DMAC and DMF) within Europe based on available HBM data:

The results of the literature search clearly indicate a data gap for exposure in the whole of Europe towards the investigated aprotic solvents (i.e., NMP, NEP, DMAC and DMF). A picture of internal exposure burden could only be attained for NMP and NEP for the German population (aged 3-17) and students in Germany (aged 20-30) as well as for DMF for students in Germany (aged 20-30).

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Gaining more knowledge on the most vulnerable and highly exposed population groups:

Due to the scarcity of available data, the knowledge gain is restricted to the German population and the age groups 3-17 and 20-30 (with further restrictions since only students were investigated).

For NMP, the daily intake (DI) decreased with increasing age, 3–5-year-old children had a 55% higher intake of NMP than adolescents aged 14–17 years (Schmied-Tobies et al., 2021).

For NEP, the daily intake (DI) increased with increasing age. Here, 3–5-year-old children had a 32% lower intake of NEP compared to adolescents aged 14–17 years (Schmied-Tobies et al., 2021).

Children and adolescents living in larger communities (≥ 100.000 inhabitants) had a higher DI of NMP compared to those living in medium-sized communities (Schmied-Tobies et al., 2021).

For NEP, low socioeconomic status was associated with a DI that was twice as high as for high socioeconomic status. This was not observed for NMP (Schmied-Tobies et al., 2021).

Furthermore, the migration background of the participants was found to be significantly associated with exposure to both NMP and NEP. Participants with a two-sided migration background had a 13% higher DI of NMP compared to those with no migration background. The DI of NEP was twice as high for this group of participants (Schmied-Tobies et al., 2021).

Assessing if internal exposure is exceeding available HBM guidance values for the aprotic solvents:

For the investigated population (German residents aged 3-17 and 20-30 years), internal exposures with NMP and NEP did not exceed the corresponding HBM-GV_{GenPop}. Even when considering a combined exposure of NMP and NEP the exposure stayed well below the guidance values. Nevertheless, it should be kept in mind that people are exposed to a variety of substances which might add to the toxicity of the investigated compounds.

For DMF data from young adults (20-30 years) from the German ESB were well below the provisional HBM-GV_{GenPop} derived for this assessment specifically.

Evaluating correlations of internal exposure with lifestyle behaviours, usage of certain products etc. based on German HBM data:

For children and adolescents exposed to floor cleaners, oven cleaners, or fabric softeners, the GM of the DI of NEP was found to be elevated by 15% to 32% compared to individuals not exposed to these products (Schmied-Tobies et al., 2021).

For participants reporting on frequent usage of body wash/shower gel or shampoo, a 53% to 73% higher exposure was found compared to those never using these products (Schmied-Tobies et al., 2021). Since both NMP and NEP are prohibited in cosmetics since 2020 (EU, 2019), this association is not expected to be in the future.

Evaluating risks of combined exposure to the reprotoxic aprotic solvents

When evaluating the risks of combined exposure to NMP and NEP it was found that the exposure data presented in the two studies from Germany (i.e., Ulrich et al., 2018 and Schmied-Tobies et al., 2021) stayed well below the newly derived HBM-GV_{GenPop}, for children, adolescents and adults.

For young adults it was possible to assess the combined exposure to NMP, NEP and DMF. It was found that the exposure data from the German ESB stayed well below the HBM-GV_{GenPop}.

Nevertheless, it should be kept in mind that people are exposed to a variety of substances which might add to the toxicity of the investigated compounds.

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Recommendations for the regulatory risk assessment:

With respect to DMF, the data recently obtained particularly within the HBM4EU by analysis of samples from the German environmental specimen bank (ESB) covering the time span 2000-2021 are showing effectiveness of regulatory measures (e.g. prohibition) being in place for cosmetic products since 2010. Over the investigated time span a decrease in concentrations of > 50% can be observed (Table 10 and Figure 2 in the full RA report; annex¹ above). In addition, restriction of DMF under Annex XVII of REACH in 2018 (however, with transitional period till 2020) could play some role as well.

As regards NMP and NEP, the HBM data available for 1991-2014 (ESB) and 2014-2017 (German Environmental Survey of Children and Adolescents V), cannot provide enough evidence for effectiveness of regulatory measures since NEP is restricted under Annex XVII of REACH in 2014 and NMP – since 2018 with transitional period till 2020. The same statement is true for prohibition of NMP and NEP in cosmetic products in EU as well being in force since 2020.

To sum up, further HMB investigations are needed to show effectiveness of regulatory measures being already in force and possible necessity for additional measures concerning NMP, NEP, DMAC and DMF exposure in a broader context covering the whole Europe.

Future prospects:

The literature search revealed the scarcity of exposure data for the European general population for the four aprotic solvents (i.e., NMP, NEP, DMAC and DMF) in question.

Monitoring for these substances in the European population is therefore recommended in the future.

Further study populations should be investigated to broaden the database on exposure to the four aprotic solvents, including susceptible subpopulations such as pregnant women.

The sources of the aprotic solvents need to be further investigated and linked to environmental monitoring in different compartments as well as to indoor air monitoring in dwellings.

Only filling of the knowledge gaps indicated above can provide answers to policy questions formulated in the Scoping document for aprotic solvents in question.

7.3 Arsenic

PQ 1. What is the current exposure of the EU population to arsenic?

On the basis of external exposure, calculated from iAs intake from diet (mean intake from diet, min – max iAs levels), EU population is exposed to: 0.05 – 0.14 µg kg⁻¹ bw/day (adolescents, adults, elderly and very elderly) or to 0.08 – 0.38 µg kg⁻¹ bw/day (infants, toddlers, other children). P95 food intake results in higher exposure (0.19 – 0.38 µg kg⁻¹ bw/day for adolescents, adults, elderly and very elderly and 0.33 - 1.23 µg kg⁻¹ bw/day for infants, toddlers and other children). HBM based estimates are in the same range – calculated average dose of all included HBM studies (excluding infants) is 0.16 µg As kg⁻¹ bw/day. HBM data included in the study did not identify any (previously unknown) higher levels of iAs exposure in the general population.

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PQ 2. What biomonitoring and exposure (environmental and occupational) data on arsenic, relevant to the European population, are currently available?

We identified 28 sets of data on populations without known sources of iAs exposure and four studies for occupationally exposed populations, all reporting speciated urinary iAs and its metabolites concentrations.

PQ 3. What is the geographic spread of the current exposure and how does it relate to different exposure sources (environmental; dietary sources)?

Due to low iAs concentrations in drinking water in most EU countries (GM 0.19 µg L⁻¹, P75 0.47 µg L⁻¹, 99 % of samples below the maximum permissible value of 10 µg L⁻¹ Banks et al. 2015), high exposure is limited to few areas with elevated As in drinking water (some areas in Italy, Hungary, Slovakia, Romania, Finland, Ireland, Greece, Croatia). For the majority of the population, diet is a main source of iAs. Calculated exposure is somewhat higher for populations that consume more seafood and/or rice.

PQ 4. Which population groups are most at risk?

- a) a) Infants followed by toddlers and other children consume most iAs per kilogram body weight, nevertheless they are also faster As metabolizers so such straightforward estimation of higher risk should be taken with caution, especially when short duration of higher exposure (per kg of body weight) is taken into account.
- b) b) Populations in the areas with elevated As in drinking water are at risk, as well as occupationally exposed individuals.

PQ 5. What factors (genetic polymorphisms) make people more susceptible or not to the risk of health effects due to arsenic exposure? How are the best and more sensitive biomarkers for identification of reliable arsenic exposure and to link to potential adverse health-effect?

Genetic polymorphisms related to metabolic rate of As (ASMT3 polymorphisms) are important as adaptation mechanisms leading in resistance to arsenic toxicity, while MTHR polymorphisms influencing folate levels could be involved in increased susceptibility to As toxicity, particularly during pregnancy with concomitant folate deficiency.

Urinary DMA is widely included as one of the markers of iAs exposure. However, it can also be excreted in urine after direct ingestion or after ingestion of less toxic arsenosugars and arsenolipids hence overestimating the exposure to iAs. Better markers are iAs and MMA, but their concentration is often so low that analytical considerations are an issue.

PQ 6. What are possible health effects resulting from chronic low exposure to arsenic from food consumption?

At long-time exposure to high iAs levels, lung, bladder and skin cancers are the most researched and confirmed outcomes. Extrapolation estimated daily dose of iAs from HBM studies (0.16 µg kg⁻¹ bw/day) results in a lifetime excess lung cancer risk of 2.7 x 10⁻⁴. This number is of the same order of magnitude as previously dietary intake calculated by EFSA based on food intake and occurrence levels in food. However, it should be noted that since the risk assessment is based on the assumption of a linear relationship between exposure and cancer risk, this approach can be considered as conservative, overestimating the risk at low exposure levels. Currently, the scientific community have not agreed whether it is possible or not to identify a threshold for the carcinogenicity of arsenic. Evaluation of the most recent dose-response data and justification of assumptions behind EFSA's dose-response, necessary to assure the currency of the dose-

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response, was beyond the scope of this work, further emphasising that the calculated risk levels must be interpreted with caution. Additional uncertainty is related to the representativeness of populations and applicability of epidemiological data, overestimation of iAs exposure in HBM studies due to the widespread presence of DMA in food, analytical challenges related to speciation of As and inter-individual differences, including individual lifestyle and susceptibility factors.

Research group preparing full arsenic report and reviewers of the report did not reach consensus on applicability of existing cancer slopes derived from high exposures to low exposures and a possible threshold for arsenic toxicity; differing views concerned specifically whether negative health effects, including cancer, are relevant at exposure levels $< 50 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in drinking water.

PQ 7. What are the best analytical methods should allow for differentiating species in urine?

Most sensitive and most widely-available analytical methods include chromatographic separation of iAs, MMA and DMA and determination of As in separated peaks with ICP-MS or HG-AFS.

Future prospects

As discussed in the full risk assessment in more detail, at this moment, there is no consensus of cancer risk of iAs in low-level exposure.

Several data are still required in a near future to allow a more accurate risk assessment:

- HBM data are missing on iAs exposure of populations consuming polluted water with As concentrations above $10 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and populations in polluted hot-spots.
- Relevant covariates (e.g. smoking, selenium nutritional status, co-exposures with other pollutants, abstinence from rice and seafood intake before sampling, past exposures) should be controlled in future HBM studies (Tsuji et al. 2021).
- Guideline values need to be harmonised.

7.4 Bisphenols

The aim of this work was to update the RA reported in the deliverable report D5.8 with new data generated in HBM4EU within the aligned studies. The risk assessment performed in Deliverable D5.8 aimed at addressing the following policy questions:

PQ 3. Are bisphenols exposure levels of concern for health?

PQ 4. Is occupational exposure of cashiers a health concern?

PQ 6. Are health risks age and gender dependent?

We concluded that the risk could be ruled out for the general population exposed to BPA, but it was not the case for bisphenol S with some RCR calculated suggesting exposures of concern. Regarding occupational exposure, available HBM data indicated that the risk from occupational exposure should not be disregarded, and that protective measures need to be taken regarding BPS exposure. Moreover, we recommended that more studies should be carried out for various occupational activities for all bisphenols.

In the aligned studies, only measurements for adults in the general population were available, thus only the first of the policy question mentioned above could be addressed in this report.

From the results of these aligned studies, the difference remains between risk assessment for BPA and BPS exposure and is due to the different choices related to the derivation for the HBM- $\text{GV}_{\text{GenPop}}$ as already discussed in the deliverable D5.8.

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Therefore, the results presented in the full RA report highlight the importance of the different initiatives currently underway for both the re-evaluation of the EFSA's t-TDI for BPA and for assessing the health effects and levels of toxicity for BPS. The outcome of this work could lead to a strengthening or the re-assessment of, one or both of the HBM-GVs_{GenPop} proposed for BPA and BPS, and of the levels of confidence associated. This could therefore change the conclusions of our risk assessment.

The EFSA Panel on Food Contact and Materials, Enzymes and Processing Aids (CEP) recently released for consultation a re-evaluation of their t-TDI set in 2015. According to this proposal, the new TDI would be established at 0.04 ng/kg bw/d of total BPA. This value is 10⁵ times lower than the current t-TDI. When recalculating the HBM-GVs for total BPA in urine for the general population, on the basis of this new TDI proposal and by the means of the PBPK model by Karrer (2018), Ineris has obtained HBM-GV divided by 10⁵ (2.3 ng/L for adults and 1.4 ng/L for children). Therefore, if this new TDI is to be confirmed after the consultation period, comparing the P95 for total BPA measured in the aligned studies to a HBM-GV derived from the new TDI proposed, would most likely result in RCR exceeding 1 by far. Thus, the risk for consumers related to BPA exposure would be of concern with regard to this new value proposed, and protective measures would need to be taken.

Still, the work presented in the full RA document, as well as in Deliverable D5.8, exemplify how biomonitoring data can be used in the risk assessment of bisphenols and also highlights the challenges and uncertainties related to its use in the bisphenols case. Moreover, the efforts to perform aligned studies in Europe are of utmost importance and must be continued to monitor on the long term the changes of the exposure of the general population in Europe to bisphenols A and S, as well as to their analogues.

7.5 Diisocyanates

PQ1. What is the current occupational exposure to diisocyanates?

The recently conducted HBM4EU occupational study on diisocyanate exposure found, in general, that diisocyanate air levels were below the binding occupational levels proposed in EU (HBM4EU Deliverable report D8.13). Unpublished Finnish HBM data, which was the main data source used in the risk assessment, also indicated low exposure to diisocyanates. In some occupational sectors, the earlier published data estimate higher exposures. There is still a need to monitor the occupational exposure to diisocyanates because a threshold limit value for BHR cannot be established.

PQ4. What are the health risks and human health impacts of the current occupational diisocyanate exposures?

In general, the excess BHR risk estimated from Finnish data was highest for MDI, especially in the construction sector where an excess BHR risk of 3.5 % was estimated. This indicates that for the Finnish construction sector, the expected excess number of BHR cases is 200. Also for HDI and TDI, the construction sector poses the highest risk: 2.9 % and 3.2 % accounting for 165 and 180 excess BHR cases in the Finnish worker population, respectively. For the other sectors (the motor and vehicle repair sector, manufacturing of PUR products and assembling of industrial products) excess risk estimates were between 1.1 – 3.0 %.

7.6 Flame retardants

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Policy question 5: How does exposure differ by geographic area within Europe? Do countries/regions have different FR exposure levels:

The available aligned study HBM data showed that there are geographical differences, as e.g. the detection frequency of certain metabolites were quite low and differs between the countries. Only in the German cohort (GerES V (sub, unweighted) study), BDCIPP and BCIPP and BCEP were detected frequently. The detected levels are in line with a previously published human biomonitoring study from Germany (Fromme et al., 2014). It should also be considered, that only in the German (GerES V (sub, unweighted)), Slovenian (SLO CRP study), Belgian (3xG study) and French (Esteban study) cohorts morning urine was used, which is normally higher concentrated and represents more realistic exposure than spot urine. This could also have an impact on the detection frequency. Regarding the dietary exposure including the food consumption data, we could not identify any significant differences.

Policy question 8: What are the relevant exposure pathways for FRs, e.g., diet, air, water, indoor environmental exposure?

We were able to provide some information that the dietary exposure pathway could have an impact on the total exposure of OPFR. Further research on e.g. the oral bioavailability and occurrence data are necessary to determine which exposure pathways (dietary or dust uptake) contribute the most to the general exposure. For now, only limited studies are available, where the dietary uptake is addressed. For flame retardants in Cat C, D and E as listed in the HMB4EU scoping document of flame retardants² almost no data are available to estimate the exposure from indoor environment (air and dust) and dietary uptake.

Future prospects

The main limitation in this risk assessment was the availability of data, e. g. occurrence data or toxicokinetic information. We were not able to estimate the daily intake of TPHP, since DPHP is also a biomarker for EHDPP. In the case that one metabolite is a biomarker for several parent compounds, it would make sense to measure other specific biomarkers (e. g. OH-TPHP, di-OH-TPHP) to estimate the exposure to e. g. TPHP. Although it might not be the main biomarker, it can still give some additional information regarding the exposure. Referring to the occurrence data, a refinement on analytical methods to achieve more sensitive LOQ and LOD is necessary to estimate the contamination. In our study, the LOQ in the food category “fats and oils” was rather high. Therefore, we do not know if an OPFR contamination in this food category is likely or not.

7.7 Lead

PQ1. What is the concentration of lead in the human blood nowadays (after phasing out leaded petrol) in the countries of Europe?

The highest proportion of children, having BLL above 20 µg/L, was identified in Slovenia, in the Upper Meža valley hot-spot, where 89% of children, aged 2–4 years had BLL GM = 47 µg/L, followed by 88% children, aged 8–10 years from the same area, with BLL GM = 41 µg/L. In addition, 10% of children in the Upper Meža valley had BLL above 100 µg/L and some of them also above 200 µg/L. In other SLO HBM studies, a small percentage (2–14%) had BLL above 20 µg/L with BLL GM between 22–33 µg/L, and none of children had BLL above 100 µg/L. In a recent Belgian HBM study (FLEHS IV), 0% of adolescents of 14–15 years had BLL above 20 µg/L. In the Czech Republic (CzechHBM-CE_2016), 5–17% of children had BLL above 20 µg/L, with BLL GM at 23 and 26 µg/L in age groups 6–11 and 3–5 years, respectively. In Germany (GerES V (sub,

² <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/hbm4eu-substances/flame-retardants/>

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unweighted), 2014–2017), the proportions of children with BLL above 20 µg/L were as follows: 7% in the age group 3–5 years, 6% in the age group 6–10 years, 3% in the age group 11–13 years, and 3% in the age group 14–17 years. The corresponding BLL GMs were 25, 23, 22 and 25 µg/L, respectively.

In adults, the highest proportion of participants with BLL above 10 µg/L were identified in Belgium FLEHS I study, where 100% of participants of 40–59 years had BLL above 10 µg/L with BLL GM at 37 µg/L. This was followed in Slovenian adults, in the Meža valley, where 98% of participants of 18–49 years had BLL above 10 µg/L, with BLL GM at 28 µg/L. In Slovenian total population, this proportion was 92%, with BLL GM at 19 µg/L, and it was higher in men than in women, 21 and 18 µg/L, respectively. In two age groups of adults in Spanish HBM, 97% of participants of 20–39 years had BLL above 10 µg/L with BLL GM at 21 µg/L, and 99% of participants of 40–59 years had BLL above 10 µg/L with BLL GM at 28 µg/L. In two age groups of Czech's adults, 75% of participants of 20–39 years had BLL above 10 µg/L with BLL GM at 19 µg/L, while in the elder group of 40–59 years, 86% had BLL above 10 µg/L with BLL GM at 23 µg/L.

The BLL still indicate exposure to lead in children especially in a part of Slovenia due to former industrial activities with lead. In adults, based on the most recent HBM data from Czech Republic (2016), exposure to lead is still indicated.

PQ2. What is the EBoD due to Pb exposure in children and adults, based on available HBM data (and potential comparison with other – selected– countries).

The environmental burden of disease (EBoD) was expressed as disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) per 100,000 people.

In children, corresponding DALYs were the highest in Slovenia in the Meža valley in general, 978–3437 (95%CI: 605–4955) per 100,000 children, which was more than 10–fold higher than in other Slovenian regions in general, 18–26 (95% CI: 11–37). This was also significantly higher than in children in selected other EU countries. In the Czech Republic, DALYs per 100,000 were 19 and 127 (considering two age groups), and between 8 and 47 in Germany (considering four age groups). In general, DALYs were higher in younger children of 3–5 years, comparing children of age between 6 and 10 years and adolescents of 11–17 years. It is also obvious from numerous studies that over time BLLs have decreased significantly (e.g. FLEHS IV and GerES V (sub, unweighted)).

In adults, corresponding DALYs were 464 (95%CI: 244–661) per 100,000 adults in Slovenia in the Meža valley versus 311 (95% CI: 161–450) in Slovenia overall. Regarding gender, DALYs were 348 (95%CI: 181–502) and 276 (95%CI: 142–399) in men and women, respectively. Based on FLEHS I study in Belgium, corresponding DALYs were calculated at 733. In two age groups of Spanish HBM, DALYs were 314 and 427, respectively. In two age groups of Czech's adults, DALYs were 385 and 546, respectively. In general, DALYs were calculated higher in elder adults, and if data were from older HBM surveys (Belgium).

PQ3. Do blood lead levels of both adults (especially pregnant women) and children still indicate permanent existence of lead exposure and what kind of exposure sources are the most important?

Blood lead levels in children and pregnant women still indicated permanent lead exposure in Slovenia, especially in the Meža valley, one of the most polluted regions in the EU and world-wide. Consequently, the calculated DALYs were the highest in this Slovenian region. When excluding these Slovenian children from the comparison with children from the other EU countries, the values were comparable.

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Based on the most recent HBM data from Belgium (FLEHS IV), none of children had BLL above 20 µg/L, while data from Germany (GerES V (sub, unweighted)) indicated only a small proportion of children that had BLL above 20 µg/L with geometric mean up to 25 µg/L. In the Czech HBM cohort (CzechHBM-CE), a higher proportion of children than in Germany had a BLL above 20 µg/L, with a geometric mean around 24 µg/L. However, this may still indicate permanent existence of lead exposure.

In adults, BLLs were higher in older data sets, e.g. in Belgium FLEHS 1 study (2004-2005) comparing to the CzechHBM-AE data from 2015. However, in the most recent data from Czech HBM, 75 to 86% of adults in two age groups had BLL higher than 10 µg/L with geometric mean around 20 µg/L, which may indicate potential permanent existence of lead exposure in European population. However, DALYs for premature deaths relating to Pb exposure could not be directly compared, since HBM data used was old. It would be worthy to perform a new survey to estimate reliable and current impacts at EU level.

Gathering of new HBM data at the EU level is highly recommended to get an overview on the current situation in the EU, as well as up to date data for a more reliable comparison and health impact assessment.

The blood lead levels still indicate exposure to lead in children especially in a part of Slovenia due to former industrial activities with lead. In adults, based on the most recent HBM data from Czech Republic (2016), exposure to lead is continuing.

7.8 Mercury and its organic compounds

PQ 1. What biomonitoring and exposure data on mercury (and its species), relevant to the European population, are currently available and what new data are needed to address policy-related questions?

There is a need for more harmonized, quality-assured human biomonitoring data of the different species of mercury on vulnerable populations. This need is more pressing for fish-consuming European nations (e.g. for Mediterranean countries, where fish consumption is similar to Spain or Portugal and the Arctic).

PQ 6. Which populations remain vulnerable to health impacts from mercury exposure and how can they be protected?

Since MeHg effects are related to neurodevelopmental diseases, children and woman of child-bearing age still remain vulnerable populations, especially in countries with a higher fish consumption. To protect them, it would be necessary to establish more awareness campaigns during pregnancy on the most suitable fish species for them and their children, which could be accompanied by regular sampling plans of methylmercury in these populations. In this frame, the HBM4EU-MOM study, which is ongoing in Spain, Portugal, Greece, Cyprus and Iceland assesses the impact of suitable fish-consumption advice to pregnant women, who were recruited through their health care providers, on scalp hair mercury.

Recommendations for the regulatory risk assessment

To establish permanent European mercury biomonitoring campaigns in order to update the current data, including those countries where no mercury human biomonitoring campaigns have been conducted. This could extend the knowledge about the possible mercury hot-spots. Regarding RA limitations, it could be interesting to harmonise the methodologies, such as those used in DEMOCOPHES study, in order to compare the results obtained from these human biomonitoring campaigns.

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Future prospects

The biomonitoring studies used in this risk assessment measured total mercury since there are no representative studies for European populations with speciation analysis of mercury. Speciation analysis is necessary to differentiate between inorganic/elemental and methyl mercury exposure. However, speciation of mercury requires complex and lengthily analytical procedures and expensive reagents and equipment, which are not routinely available in analytical laboratories. The development of harmonized methodologies and their use to monitor levels of mercury and mercury compounds in vulnerable populations in Europe, would allow an adequate characterization of the most suitable matrices for each type of mercury. The selection of best-suited matrices and biomarkers of exposure is crucial and there is still great uncertainty in the conversion ratios between the different matrices to carry out the risk assessments. Therefore, an adequate characterization of each species in the human matrices would contribute to reduce the uncertainties of the evaluation.

To relate the steady state concentration in blood with the average daily intake of mercury a one-compartment toxicokinetic model is used (WHO, 1990). The one-compartment model is the simplest form of a pharmacokinetic model in that the entire body is assumed to act like a single, uniform entity that uses only one volume term, the apparent volume of distribution. In comparison, the PBPK models typically includes several pharmacokinetic parameters (e.g., tissue volumes, partition coefficients, rate constants for metabolism and elimination), thus, PBPK models are conceptually more accurate in predicting body burden of MeHg (e.g., internal dose) as compared to one-compartment models. Development of PBPK model for mercury for better risk assessment is one of the tasks that WP12 is doing. This PBPK model once validated will allow a more refined risk assessment for mercury.

All the guideline values that have been considered the most appropriate in this evaluation (TWI, HBM-I and provisional HMG) are derived from the same PoD obtained from the Faroe Islands and Seychelles cohorts, considering neurodevelopment as the effect most relevant, however, a greater consensus should be reached on the endpoints that are analysed in these and other cohorts. Furthermore, crucial aspects such as the determination of the appropriate PoDs for immunotoxicity and cardiovascular effects, and the estimation of corresponding guidance values, if necessary, remain unaddressed. This would allow refining risk assessments.

7.9 Mycotoxins

PQ: Is the risk associated to human exposure to these mycotoxins characterised?

Results obtained in the present report confirmed that the European population is exposed to DON and that a fraction of this population is, to some extent, exposed to levels that might represent a potential health concern. The risk associated with the exposure to DON for the European population is now characterized.

Regarding the risk characterization associated with exposure to FB₁, due to a high uncertainty associated with estimates, it was not considered adequate to include it in the present assessment.

PQ: Is it possible to set a HBM guidance value for mycotoxins?

The establishment of an HBM-GV for DON was performed under the task 5.2, and it is considered of major importance for these assessments, contributing to a significant decrease in uncertainty. The HBM-GV was determined considering a BMDL₀₅ of 0.11 mg DON/kg bw/day, reduced body weight gain as the critical effect, and a factor for metabolic conversion of 0.14 (HBM4EU Deliverable report D5.9, Section "Derivation of a HBM Guidance Value (HBM-GV) for Deoxynivalenol (DON): HBM-GVGenPop for the general population").

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Recommendations for the regulatory risk assessment

The inclusion of mycotoxins' HBM data in risk assessment is important since it represents the internal exposure dose from all sources and by all routes of exposure at individual level, thus reducing the uncertainties associated with risk assessment performed at population level and/ or indirect approaches (e.g., through combination of occurrence in food and food consumption data) (Choi et al. 2015). The use of HBM data for mycotoxins (and other compounds) implies an extensive knowledge of metabolism and there are still some gaps regarding mycotoxins' toxicokinetic data that may hamper a proper risk assessment. If a risk assessment is developed for regulatory purposes, all these aspects are important for consideration and will assume a high relevance.

The establishment of an HBM-GV is of major relevance for performing a more accurate risk characterization, allowing a direct comparison of exposure obtained through HBM with a reference value, and reducing the uncertainty in estimates. However, regarding compounds for which a reduced knowledge on metabolism is available, the issue of uncertainty in estimates remains and the limitations of the HBM-GV should be described in detail.

Considering the present assessment, the use of HBM data for risk assessment encompasses some limitations that are related with the use of data published in several scientific articles, non-harmonized sample collection and criteria for left-censored data. These limitations were overcome by using HBM data available from the HBM4EU aligned studies, with results obtained in field campaigns using harmonized procedures and analytical methods subjected to a previous quality-control exercise. The limitations may be surpassed in a near future by developing of guidance for setting-up biomonitoring campaigns that allow a proper comparison among studies results and with the HBM-GV.

Future prospects

There are several aspects still requiring further analysis in a near future to allow a more accurate risk assessment:

- The development of more studies to assess exposure in eastern European countries to ensure an adequate exposure assessment throughout all European regions.
- The importance of setting up guidelines for developing biomonitoring studies (for general population and workers) with harmonized procedures to enhance comparison of results between different studies.
- New biomarkers of exposure are not needed since the main metabolites are already identified for DON; however, it is important the development of analytical standards to ensure better analytical measurements and consequently a more accurate exposure assessment.
- The use of 24h urine samples to decrease the uncertainty related to the use of HBM-GV calculated for 24h samples, even considering the associated burden for the participant.

7.10 PAHs

PQ1: How high is the current (year 2012 or more recent) exposure (both external and internal) of the EU population (working and general) to data-rich substances?

The most recent values obtained in the HBM4EU aligned studies show that the levels of internal exposure in the European population, in adults of the general population, are similar to those from previous studies published in the literature. We have no indications that the newly obtained HBM

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data for 1-OHPyr were substantially lower than the ones previously measured and reported in the open literature.

PQ2: Are the overall exposure levels in the general population, children, and pregnant women above any health-relevant assessment levels (reference dose or HBM guidance values)?

No analysis was done on stratified data since there are no reference values for that.

Considering the indicative tolerable cancer risk level for the general population proposed by the EC (2001) at levels of 10⁻⁶, the ELCR results obtained in the present work for 4 of the 7 countries included in the aligned studies (Luxembourg (A_LNS_Oriscav-Lux2), France (A_ANSP_ESTEBAN), Czech Republic (A_MU_(C)ELSPAC) and Poland(A_NIOM_POLAES)), all in the 10⁻⁵ range, are of concern.

The mean dietary intake estimated by EFSA based on the occurrence of PAHs in food is, in general, one order of magnitude higher than that estimated daily intake from exposure reconstruction based on the available HBM4EU data (mean values). This is probably due to the conservative nature of the bottom-up approaches to exposure estimation, compared to the one that is based on HBM data reconstruction. As such, the ELCR estimates based on EFSA's PAH4 intake levels is higher than the risk calculated from intake estimates based on HBM data exposure reconstruction, because the dietary intake estimates are higher.

Further, an assumption that pyrene intake is represented by the biomarker 1-OHP in urine and presented as PAH4 intake needs to be taken with caution, since there are some doubts and uncertainties whether 1-OH pyrene is a reliable bioindicator of measured dietary polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon under normal conditions (Viau et al., 2002). In addition, pyrene is not classified as carcinogenic and monitoring of its metabolite for the purpose of risk assessment is only based on the assumption that the level of 1-OHPyr correlate to some extent with BaP and other carcinogenic species co-occurring commonly with pyrene in PAHs mixtures. In addition, exposure to PAHs mixture may modify metabolism or induce different effects, therefore a single metabolite may not adequately characterize exposure to PAHs.

PQ3: What are knowledge gaps and related research needs for data-rich substances to answer the questions above satisfactorily in the following years (Year 3)? Can the identified knowledge gaps be mended based on existing data or by extension of current good HBM?

New HBM4EU aligned studies provided recent data on other 11 PAHs and metabolites, such as 1-hydroxynaphthalene, 9-hydroxyfluorene 4-hydroxyphenanthrene. However, there are no available health-based guidance values for internal exposure for PAHs metabolites that would help to interpret the HBM results, and to put the results in a health risk context. Deriving future HBM-GVs for these metabolites would allow further RA for these compounds.

7.11 Pesticides

7.11.1 Chlorpyrifos and chlorpyrifos-methyl

The most relevant policy questions to be answered by this work are as follows:

PQ: Are the exposure levels of health-relevance/concern for vulnerable groups (infants, children and pregnant women) or high exposure population groups (e.g., occupational exposure)?

- The monitoring data confirms concerns and potential concerns for several population groups, highlighting that the risk for children is clearly higher than for adults.

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PQ: How can cumulative risks of pesticide mixtures on health outcomes be assessed and integrated in regulation?

PQ: Is it possible to establish EU wide accepted health-based guidance values for the pesticides, preferably taking potential mixture effects and evidence from epidemiological studies into account?

- The urinary marker TCPy covers only two closely related active substances, chlorpyrifos and chlorpyrifos-methyl, and thus it is not relevant, per se, for covering cumulative risk to pesticides mixtures. However, the combination of the more specific urinary marker, TCPy, with a second biomarker, based on urinary levels of alkyl phosphate metabolites, common to several other pesticides, would allow setting human biomonitoring programmes including a screening tier, using markers common to a large number of active substances and a refined tier if the markers for the screening are exceeded. This kind of programmes would facilitate the implementation and prioritisation of human biomonitoring.

Recommendations for the regulatory risk assessment

Chlorpyrifos and chlorpyrifos-methyl are no longer authorised in the EU and all MRLs are set at the default value. As indicated above, these results based on real human exposure support this decision. Nevertheless, it should be noted that a similar assessment conducted with the “legally binding ADI” at the time of the monitoring would have result in very different risk characterisation results. The results confirm the need for rapid regulatory implementation of the scientific updates on pesticide toxicity.

Future prospects

As mentioned above, the combination or TCP with a second biomarker, based on urinary levels of alkyl phosphate metabolites, should be considered for future activities.

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7.11.2 Pyrethroid mixture

The most relevant policy questions to be answered by this work are as follows:

PQ: Are the exposure levels of health-relevance/concern for vulnerable groups (infants, children and pregnant women) or high exposure population groups (e.g., occupational exposure)?

Generally, the data suggests a low concern for the general population. However, for some highly exposed children, a risk cannot to be excluded and uncertainties remain, warranting further considerations. These include e.g. uncertainties related to the developmental neurotoxicity since ADIs given for many pyrethroids (and used for the RA) are based on neurotoxicity observed in adult experimental animals, which may not sufficiently protect against developmental neurotoxicity during pregnancy/early infancy.

PQ: How can cumulative risks of pesticide mixtures on health outcomes be assessed and integrated in regulation?

PQ: Is it possible to establish EU wide accepted health-based guidance values for the pesticides, preferably taking potential mixture effects and evidence from epidemiological studies into account?

This work provides a model for the setting of a provisional HBM screening value for combined pyrethroid exposure and for its use in the assessment of the risks of pyrethroid mixtures. The same approach might be taken for other pesticides to identify those for which a health risk cannot be excluded.

PQ: How can HBM data from HBM4EU feed into prioritisation of the pesticides for risk assessments and regulatory decision-making?

See below.

Recommendations for the regulatory risk assessment and future prospects

It is proposed that possibilities to use HBM for post-marketing surveillance is evaluated systematically as part of EU (re)evaluation of pesticides. This would mean that there are analytical methods, sufficient toxicokinetic data available and suitable metabolites for HBM studies. HBM-GVs corresponding to external ADI levels should be derived whenever possible. The applicants of authorization of active ingredients should be requested to provide their proposals on the biomonitoring of their active ingredients. A respective section could be included in the overall pesticide evaluation (Volume 1 of the DAR/RAR) and would be subject to peer review by MSs.

7.12 PFAS mixture

The RA report and its findings contribute to answering policy questions #1 and #11 of the HBM4EU PFAS scoping document ³.

PQ11. How can mixture effects of environmental and human PFASs mixtures present to date be estimated?

Various approaches were available and further developed to estimate the risk resulting from exposure to mixtures of PFASs. In that respect, our aim was to refine the mixture risk assessment of PFASs taking three approaches for comparison, the Relative Potency Factor (RPF) approach,

³ https://www.hbm4eu.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/HBM4EU_D4.9_Scoping_Documents_HBM4EU_priority_substances_v1.0-PFAS.pdf

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the Hazard Index (HI) approach, and the sum value approach of the European Food Safety Agency (EFSA). The latter approach uses the EFSA tolerable weekly intake (TWI) value for the sum of PFOA, PFNA, PFHxS, and PFOS. The HI and RPF approach were adapted specifically with the purpose of being able to use human biomonitoring data as primary input to the risk assessment.

PQ 1. What is the current exposure of the EU population to PFASs and do they exceed Guidance values (reference and HBM values), where available?

All three risk assessment approaches indicate that PFAS exposure exceeds Guidance values, and thus may cause adverse health effects in certain segments of the European population, thereby confirming the conclusion drawn in the recent EFSA scientific opinion. It should be mentioned that this report is meant as a scientific exploration of how to use HBM in risk assessment. This exercise explores various approaches to perform mixture risk assessment for PFASs that are based on pragmatism and available data and therefore have their underlying assumptions, limitations and uncertainties.

Future prospects

This mixture risk assessment illustrated that human biomonitoring data are very valuable to calculate the cumulative risk resulting from exposure to PFASs. It is inherent to human biomonitoring to reflect the aggregated exposure from different exposure routes and exposure sources. It should be mentioned that this RA was meant as a scientific exploration of how to use HBM in risk assessment. The exercise explored various approaches to perform mixture risk assessment for PFASs that are based on pragmatism and available data and therefore have their underlying assumptions, limitations and uncertainties. We concluded based on our mixture risk assessment, that the combined exposure to PFASs in certain segments of the European population is too high and may give rise to adverse human health effects, thereby confirming the conclusion drawn in the recent EFSA scientific opinion.

For future research, we have the following recommendations that would facilitate the use of human biomonitoring of PFASs in (mixture) risk assessment:

- In general, we observed that risk assessments, based on data obtained from studies that relied on relatively high LOD and LOQ, are very uncertain. We therefore stress the need for improving the analytical methods for biomonitoring and for bringing down the LOD and LOQ;
- We highly recommend performing studies that observe paired blood-urine samples to have a better insight into exposure to short-chain PFASs;
- For a refined mixture risk assessment, we recommend considering mixture exposure at the individual level rather than using summary statistics for the summation of exposure to multiple compounds;
- It is preferable to include exposure and effect data in the risk assessment at the individual level. This would solve problems regarding difficulties in point of departure setting. Furthermore, these data may be used to study relative potencies among PFASs at the human level and may be used to observe associations of PFAS mixture exposure with adverse health outcomes to improve direct estimation of adverse health effects upon combined exposure to PFASs.
- We recommend validating relative potencies of PFASs for other effects, sex, life-stages, and species, and in particular for critical effects such as immune effects;

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- In line with this, we recommend – if feasible - to develop a human-based in vitro/ex vivo model for immunotoxicity that can mimic the in vivo response.
- We advise, complementary to this, to investigate mode(s) of action and adverse outcome pathways for PFASs to overcome data gaps and to shed light on species concordance.

7.13 UV-filter benzophenone-3

The aim was to assess the exposure levels in the European population and to determine whether those exposure levels are safe in relation to the toxicological properties of benzophenone-3. Additionally, this report considered how Human Biomonitoring data can inform the risk assessment case of benzophenone-3, whether the necessary tools can be acquired, and if this information is useful for policymakers. By answering these questions, we respond to policy questions 2, 6, and 9 from the scoping document on UV-filters:

What are current levels of exposure of the EU population to benzophenone UV-filters?

How effective was the restriction of BP-3 in reducing exposures in the EU population?

How can HBM4EU results feed into regulatory decisions and risk assessments (ECHA and EFSA)?

Exposure was assessed with a meta-analysis of the biomonitoring data and in six of the aligned studies. The 3 studies from literature included BP-3 concentrations measured in urine samples in cohorts from Denmark, Belgium, and Spain that were sampled between 2010 and 2013. The six aligned studies that included BP-3 were performed in Germany, Luxembourg, Sweden, Norway, Spain, and Poland and samples were taken between 2014 and 2018.

The meta-analysis resulted in exposure estimates ranging from 0.60 to 4.40 µg/g creatinine for the average population, and 16.30 to 392.00 µg/g creatinine for the highly exposed population. In the aligned studies, the typical case BP-3 exposure based on the P50 ranged from <LOQ to 3.68 µg/g creatinine and the reasonable worst-case exposure, based on the P95, ranged from 18.97 to 68.83 µg/g creatinine. The most sensitive endpoint for the hazardous properties of benzophenone-3 was reproductive toxicity. The derived provisional HBM guidance value was 340 µg/g creatinine. The outcome of the new risk assessment showed that indeed the P50 and P95 are lower in the more recent measurements. Of the six new studies the highest RCR at the P95 was 0.2, where it was 1.15 in the previous assessment. However, an important note is that the highly exposed cohort in the previous assessment was not included in the aligned studies, while the other cohorts from literature had similar exposure levels to those in the aligned studies. In general, higher exposure levels were found in woman than in men in the new studies. No clear influence was found of age or sample regime.

This preliminary risk assessment of BP-3 implied that in general there is no risk indicated to the population included in the aligned studies. It also shows that there are notable differences in exposure between groups, with the most highly exposed groups approaching (but not surpassing) the acceptable risk levels for BP-3. This information is valuable input for regulatory authorities as it provides insight in real-life exposures, which can be used to refine regulatory risk assessments and assess the effectiveness of regulation.

Future prospects

The risk assessment of BP-3 could be further refined by more substance-specific toxicokinetic research. Further toxicokinetic evidence on BP-3 metabolism and elimination might improve the reliability of the F_{ue} and allow for more precise consideration of metabolites. Moreover, if stronger evidence arises that this substance has the potential to accumulate in humans, it may be

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worthwhile to study exposure in another matrix such as the blood. Incorporation of HBM data on BP-3 metabolites could improve the precision of the BP-3 exposure assessment. Furthermore, methods should be developed to study possible mixture effects of exposure to BPs that need to be included in the assessment besides BP-3's metabolites (i.e. BP-1).

More detailed research on contribution of exposure sources of BP-3 to internal dose would benefit the relevance of HBM data in risk management. The advantage of HBM data is that actual aggregated exposure is determined, but for risk management also insight in exposure sources is needed to know if and to what extent the study population was exposed to the product that is being regulated.

The outcome of the studies shows that HBM data can provide useful insights in identifying highly exposed groups. Time-trend analysis based on HBM can quantify the actual population-wide effects of specific policy changes. By giving insight in total exposure from all sources and routes, HBM can be a valuable aid in the one substance one assessment goal of the new Chemical Strategy for Sustainability, in particular for substances as BP-3 which falls under multiple regulations.

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